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for Democracy

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Deliverable Abstract

This deliverable provides a conceptual overview of some of the problems AI and big data pose to democracy from an institutional perspective. Module D focuses on the use of personal data and user profiling. Module E focuses on the control of individual speech and action. Later versions of this deliverable will provide an actionable toolkit.

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Definition
ADM	Automated Decision Making
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI Act	Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council Laying Down Harmonised Rules on Artificial Intelligence and Amending Certain Union Legislative Acts
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy AI
Big Data	An enormous collection of data. These data sets also tend to continually grow and evolve with time. These data banks are typically so large that they cannot be stored via regular means, nor processed via traditional data-processing methods.
D1.1 DMP	Deliverable 1.1 Data Management Plan
ECHR	The European Convention on Human Rights
EEA	European Economic Area
ePrivacy Directive	ePrivacy directive (2002/58/EFC, as revised by 2009/136/EC)

EPRS	European Parliamentary Research Service
EU	European Union
FER	Facial Emotion Recognition
FRT	Facial Recognition Technology
GDPR	Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the protection of natural persons with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data, and repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation)
HLEG	High-Level Expert Group on Artificial Intelligence
IoT	Internet of Things
JOIC	Jersey Office of the Information Commissioner
LfdI BW	The State Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information in Baden-Württemberg
LLM	Large Language Model
ML	Machine Learning
NLP	Natural Language Processing
OECD	Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development
OPCC	Office of the Privacy Commissioner of Canada
The Charter	Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union
User Profiling	The process of generating data-driven descriptions of individuals
VAE	Variational Autoencoder
VR	Virtual Reality
WP	Work Package
WP29	Article 29 Working Party

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Module D: Personal Data and User Profiling

Executive Summary

This document is currently composed of work undertaken in task 4.1 of the KT4D project which aims to conceptualise the current state of the art in regard to the impact of AI and big data on democracy from the perspective of governments, companies, and organisations. Later versions of this document will incorporate work from task 4.2 to advance the state of the art. This report constitutes one of the five modules (module D) of the social risk toolkit being developed with KT4D.

This module aims to understand and conceptualise the threats and risks of the use of personal data and user profiling from an institutional and collective perspective. In doing so, the work contained in this module hopes to contribute to the protection of human rights and democratic values, one of the KERs of KT4D. The robust definitions of risks and threats provided in this module also serve as an actionable basis for work in WPs 5, 6 and 7. The conceptualisation of the problems that the use of personal data and user profiling pose will provide the basis for the development of a social risk toolkit later in the project.

This document conceptualises the current concerns about knowledge technologies and the use of personal data and user profiling on democratic institutions. In **Section 1** we provide a brief introduction and overview of knowledge technologies, and their use of personal data and user profiling. In **Section 2** we outline and highlight five categories of problems that AI and big data pose to democracy. These include problems concerning equality, privacy, transparency, accountability, and democratic participation. In **Section 3** we begin to map the current regulatory frameworks. Finally, **Section 4** outlines the proposed work for task 4.2 including the development of the social risk toolkit to advance the state of the art.

1 Introduction

1.1 Overview

Given the current speed of advancements in the development of knowledge technologies, particularly AI, a thorough analysis of the key concepts and their risks is crucial. The analysis included in this module is based on a literature review and applied philosophical analysis. This version of the module focuses on conceptualising and robustly defining risks that the use of personal data and user profiling pose from an institutional perspective.

1.1.1 Structure

This version of Module D: Personal Data and User Profiling serves as a preliminary review and conceptual overview of the problems AI and big data pose to democracy. In the following sections of this introduction, we provide definitions of knowledge technologies, personal data, and user profiling, and outline some democratic values, which will serve as the basis for the rest of the report. Section 2 provides descriptions of some of the problems posed by the use of personal data and user profiling under three themes: policy making and equality, democratic deliberation, and surveillance. Section 3 outlines our work to map and analyse current regulatory frameworks. Finally, section 4 proposes some of the future work to be undertaken in task 4.2 to develop a social risk toolkit.

1.1.2 Scope and Limitations

This version of module D as part of deliverable 4.1 precedes work within WP4 that will advance ethical and legal considerations of the use of personal data and user profiling. As such, this version only serves to provide a conceptual overview of some of the issues that arise within the literature, rather than an actionable framework, which will be developed in task 4.2. The concepts and analysis included in module D will form the basis of state of the art for WPs 5, 6, and 7 to draw upon. Later versions of this module will focus on developing an actionable social toolkit which rests upon the concepts defined in this version. Further work to develop this toolkit will be undertaken in task 4.2.

1.2 What are Knowledge Technologies?

Knowledge technologies, as distinct from information technologies, have been defined in the Module C of the social risk toolkit. Within KT4D, knowledge technologies are thus defined as technologies which support and contribute to the creation and dissemination of knowledge.

Rather than conceptualise the notion of knowledge technologies under a personal data and user profiling lens, this section will build upon this existing definition and define the terms ‘personal data’ and ‘user

profiling’ in sections 1.2.1 and 1.2.2 respectively. Beginning with a brief history of the terms, each section will outline some common uses of personal data and user profiling.

1.2.1 Personal Data

Personal data, as defined by the European Commission (2018), “is any information that relates to an identified or identifiable living individual”. This can include but is of course not limited to, names, addresses, special category data, biometric and genetic data, and health data.

To better understand the importance of personal data, it seems important to understand its place in the data ecosystem. Drawing on the distinction made in Module C between knowledge and information, data leads to information when it is organised and interpreted. With an ever-expanding range of technologies that monitor, generate, and collect data about us, both the data and the technology that does this have intersected almost all aspects of our lives, including civic participation.

If data is collected from us and about us, then the question arises as to who *owns* personal data. The debate seems to converge on the idea that data subjects are the default data owners (Al-Khouri, 2012; Hummel, et al., 2021; Black, 2021; Zang, 2023). The strength of this ownership and the rights it confers however is hotly debated (Hummel, et al., 2021).¹ Regardless of ownership data, for better or for worse, has become redefined in the technology space as a kind of currency in the digital age (Schwartz, 2003: 2056). Data, and by extension personal data, has therefore typically been understood as valuable almost exclusively in a financial, or commodity, sense. There is an emerging countertrend however to understand data as a public good. Drawing on information economists such as Stiglitz (1999) and Varian (1999), Taylor (2016: 2) notes that data is a public good if we see it as ‘non-rivalrous’ and ‘non-excludable’. The concept of big data however creates a system where data becomes ‘functionally excludable’ because of the value the private sector gains by controlling it (Taylor, 2016: 2).

‘Small data’ (our individual personal data) becomes big data when aggregated into larger datasets (Lupton, 2018: 1). Whilst we often understand big data in terms of the anonymous datasets that institutions and corporations collect and utilise, Lupton (2018: 2) introduces the idea of ‘personal big data’ to understand the experiences and sense-making of people navigating the way their data is collected and used. In particular the collection of data from social media has made it incredibly easy to gather information about people. For example, studies have shown that by merely looking at likes on Facebook, algorithms can correctly predict the political affiliation of individuals 85% of the time (Tufekci, 2017). This has ramifications in the political context. We cannot simply unplug and disengage, and so the inevitable effects of the use of our personal data need to be understood, mitigated, or changed if we are to navigate this merging of knowledge technologies and data into our everyday lives.

¹ For an in-depth discussion of the varying views of data ownership see Hummel, Braun and Dabrock (2021) who systemise these views under four themes: the modes that can be used to control data; commodification of data; protection of data versus data as a tool for the common good; and individual versus collective claims of data as property.

1.2.2 User Profiling

Coupling personal data with information about user preferences, interests, and behaviours has created the opportunity to develop profiles of types of users, or more recently *specific* users, based on certain metrics. User profiling can therefore be described as the process of generating data-driven descriptions or “virtual representations” of individuals (Cufoglu, 2014: 1). The data that makes up a user profile may differ in each use case, however it is typically a mix of data that has been explicitly given by the user (for example, when signing up to a social media site you may give your name, age, and location), or may be ‘learnt’ or predicted based on user behaviour. User profiles are used in a variety of domains that span all aspects of our digital lives, such as social media, online news outlets, and our calendar management systems (Schiaffino and Amandi, 2009: 193). User profiling techniques present a unique opportunity for governments, institutions, and private organisations to correlate data about both groups of people, and specific individuals (Hildebrandt, 2008b: 303).

Hildebrandt (2008a: 26) argues for an understanding of profiling from a knowledge generation perspective. We may for example want to understand profiling as a way to generate “discovery-driven”, or data-driven, hypotheses which can then be tested once the profiles are applied to specific contexts (Hildebrandt, 2008a: 18-19). Some questions then arise as to who is using these profiles, in what ways they are used, and the effects accuracy, and inaccuracy, of these profiles can have on democracy.

One such use of user profiling is in recommender systems. The ways we want to be able to access information online have increasingly become more individualistic. As such, recommender systems have become increasingly individualised to cater to our want of personalised information – something that is possible given the sheer amount of data available (Eke, et al., 2019: 144907). Recommender systems in part rely on user profiling to recommend content to us and reduce the time we spend searching for information (Roy & Dutta, 2022: 1-3).

1.2.3 Automated Decision-Making

Automated decision-making (ADM) is perhaps the most common thematic under which the effects of AI on democracy have been discussed. AI systems can assist or replace human decision-makers in various domains, such as public administration, health care, education and justice. While these systems may offer benefits such as efficiency, accuracy, and consistency of decisions, they also pose significant challenges for democratic values and institutions. These challenges include the lack of transparency, accountability and participation in the design of AI systems as well as the potential for algorithmic bias and discrimination. The ethical and social implications of delegating human agency to machines is a further issue. This deliverable will in part focus on conceptualising the challenges that ADM poses, particularly from the use of user profiling within ADM systems.

1.3 The Value of Democracy

There are both instrumental and intrinsic reasons to value democracy. In short, democracy is valuable instrumentally because (1) democracy can assist us in producing laws and policies that protect the rights and interests of citizens, (2) democracy more often than other systems produces the right laws and policies (there are epistemic benefits to democratic decision-making), and (3) democracy can improve the people in it through increased autonomy and knowledge (Christiano and Bajaj, 2022). Intrinsic reasons to value democracy include self-governance and liberty, the value of public justification and deliberation, and the promotion of equality. We take each of these valuable aspects in turn.

Concerning the instrumental value of democracy, other governmental structures, for example oligarchy or dictatorships, do not protect the rights and interests of citizens as well. Landemore (2013: 3) for example argues that “a democratic decision procedure is likely to be a better decision procedure than any non-democratic decision procedures, such as a council of experts or a benevolent dictator” because of the epistemic benefits gained from civic participation and democratic deliberation. There are also strong correlations to be found between democracies and the protection of core rights (Landman, 2018).

One way to conceptualise these epistemic benefits include Condorcet’s Jury Theorem (Condorcet, 1785).² Other ways to understand the epistemic benefits of democracy include the notion of cognitive diversity (Waldron, 1995), the idea that diversity can trump ability (Landemore, 2013; Hong and Page, 2004), and the fact that the citizens within democracies may be better placed to understand and identify problems in society, even if experts may be needed to devise the best solution (Dewey and Rogers, 2012). Condorcet’s Jury Theorem suggests that if we assume that voters are competent, sincere, and statistically independent of each other, then the probability of the right decision being made increases the more voters there are. These conditions however are not always met. For example, voters may lack independence (Anderson, 2008: 133; Estlund, 2008), or importantly in the context of AI and big data, some groups may have better or different access to information than others. Finally, we may instrumentally value democracy because of the autonomy and active decision-making role it confers to its citizens. Concerning intrinsic reasons to value democracy, we may value democracy because it ensures citizens have the ability to self-govern (Gould, 1988), the laws democracies make are publicly justified (Habermas, 1996), and it protects and promotes equality amongst its citizens.

There are of course multiple forms and degrees of democracy which offer varying levels of freedom to their citizens. This section has only sought to discuss the benefits of democracy if it were employed in an ideal setting. In reality increasing political polarisation and the erosion of the power of elected representatives may see some democracies move closer to illiberal ones. This is of particular importance to KT4D as the use of knowledge technologies may differ and produce different outcomes under varying levels of citizen freedom. Later versions of this Module, and the social risk toolkit as a whole, will explore the implications of the use of knowledge technologies in different democratic contexts.

² For more on Condorcet’s Jury Theorem see Barry (1965), Cohen (1986), Grofman and Feld (1988), and Goodin and Spiekerman (2019).

2 Risks from the use of personal data and user profiling

This section outlines some threats from the use of personal data and user profiling. These threats are categorised into five themes: equality, privacy, transparency, accountability, and participation. Each of these themes will be taken in turn to explain their importance, and outline some of the ways they can be undermined by AI and big data.

2.1 Equality

Equality is by-and-large considered both a positive aspect of democracy, and a necessary feature for democracy. To be brief, the main benefit of equality in democracy is that it gives equal consideration to all individuals, thus each person is a free and willing self-legislator among equals. It can also be seen as a necessary condition too (as we know it), since it seems that in order to freely deliberate, and reach legitimate democratic decisions, no individual (qua citizen) should be given greater preferential treatment, if decisions are to be made ‘democratically’ (Fleming, 1993). This is not to deny that individuals may have greater power in democracy than others, for example, MPs in the UK have a greater deal of legislative power than a regular citizen. However, by virtue of citizenship everyone (and anyone) in-principle, could hold legislative office. Thus, regardless of where and to what degree democratic procedures are equal, at some point equality plays a part.

As democratic deliberation has moved, at least in part, online, this has placed some of the power over our deliberation into the hands of private firms and away from individual citizens (Manheim and Kaplan, 2019: 152-153). Ultimately this infringes on equality since these firms can prioritise themselves and those whose interests align with their own. Moreover, relying on the analysis of big data and user profiling places moves this power, not just into the hands of private firms, but also into the algorithms used to target and sort the information we access.

There are many issues that arise in terms of (lack of) equality from the use of user profiling. Here we outline three such issues: access to information because of algorithmic targeting and sorting, and problems of bias for equality in decision-making. We take each of these in turn.

2.1.1 Access to Information

In order to make informed decisions, citizens must be able to access information. As has been explored in previous sections of the social risk toolkit, the ways in which we access information has changed with the development of knowledge technologies. In particular, social media has changed the way citizens participate in democracy, with citizens now playing more of a role in content creation and dissemination than we have previously seen (Kneuer, 2106: 666-667). Stewart, Cichocki and McLeod (2022) outline some of the ways that AI-driven algorithms on social media sort and target information. This unequal access to information exacerbates societal harms, for example epistemic injustice and social distrust (Stewart, et al., 2022). These ideas however can also meaningfully be translated into other uses of AI-driven algorithms in other knowledge

technologies such as search engines. As outlined in section 1.2.2, user profiling is often used within these algorithms to create a more personalised experience for users. In doing so, the information that individual citizens have immediate, and perhaps passive, access to varies according to their user profile. This section draws on Stewart, Cichocki and McLeod's (2022) distinction between algorithmic sorting and algorithmic targeting to better understand the risks of user profiling in social media and search engine systems. Relatedly, we may also think the processes of algorithmic targeting and sorting of information poses threats to transparency if users are unaware of the way information is presented to them. The relationship of equal access to information and transparency will be explored in section 2.3.

2.1.1.1 Algorithmic Sorting and Filter Bubbles

The process of algorithmic sorting, as described by Stewart, Cichocki and McLeod (2022: 6) is “the increasing separation of people on social media into different epistemic worlds, which have little overlap in informational content”. This term does not describe the technical processes of sorting algorithms, but rather the effects that various social media and search engine algorithms have on how information is categorised.

One such effect is the development of filter bubbles. Whilst we often praise social media, search engines and other online tools for increasing our access to diverse viewpoints, the use of algorithms based on user profiles can actually have the opposite effect (Bozdag & van der Hoven, 2015: 249-250). Filter bubbles then are a form of algorithmic sorting that is ultra-personalised, invisible to us, and something we do not choose to enter (Pariser, 2011: 9-10). Because of this, filter bubbles are distinct from echo chambers, which are the effect of human agency and our self-selection into groups (Stewart, Cichocki and McLeod (2022: 7) offer Facebook groups as an example of such self-selection online), although our own choosing of information we want to see of course feeds into the user profiling that underpins filter bubbles.

Filter bubbles pose a threat to democracy and public deliberation in many ways. Bozdag and van der Hoven (2015: 255) identify different risks according to different conceptions of democracy. For example, under a liberal view of democracy, the restriction of users' liberty and unawareness of other viewpoints are paramount (Bozdag & van der Hoven, 2015: 255). Under a deliberative view of democracy, we may identify the negative effects to civic discourse, commonground, and the decreasing of epistemic quality within society (Bozdag & van der Hoven, 2015: 255).³ Whatever conception of democracy is understood however, what seems to be important is that filter bubbles undermine civic participation because of the constraining of information and deliberation to highly personalised groups.

Even if the effects of algorithmic sorting resulting in filter bubbles may be overstated within the literature, the process of algorithmic sorting itself poses many issues for democratic institutions and civic participation. The first is that algorithmic sorting can reify societal issues, in particular testimonial injustice (Stewart, et al., 2022: 12-19). Testimonial injustice is a form of epistemic injustice, as coined by Miranda Fricker (2007). Epistemic injustice is a kind of injustice that wrongs someone in their capacity as a knower (Fricker, 2007: 1). Testimonial injustice is the primary form of epistemic injustice, and “occurs when prejudice causes a hearer to give a deflated level of credibility to a speaker's word” (Fricker, 2007: 1). This can be both systematic or

³ The effects on epistemic quality and our epistemic communities are discussed in Module E.

incidental (Fricker, 2007: 28-29). Essentially, testimonial injustice occurs when someone’s word is not seen as credible because the person listening has some prejudice against the speaker, for example someone who holds racist views may not give a person of colour’s testimony about racism they face the credibility the testimony deserves. Algorithmic sorting can exacerbate testimonial injustices that are already present in society, for example the testimonial injustice that marginalised groups face because citizens are sorted into increasingly distant online communities, and contribute to Othering (Stewart, et al., 2022: 14).

Social media and search engine algorithms based on user profiling therefore pose significant risks to democracy because of the way they sort, and thus constrain, the information citizens can see and have easy access to. Of course, it may well be the case that citizens can still seek out alternative information, however the information we passively consume via social media feeds (especially with the advent of recommendation feeds rather than chronological feeds) is constrained by these filter bubbles and algorithmic sorting based on user profiling.

2.1.1.2 Targeting and Dark Advertising

Algorithmic targeting utilises user profiling in order to provide content based on the likelihood that the user will engage with it (Stewart, et al., 2022: 9). We may not see the targeting of information to users as particularly harmful, after all targeted advertising and recommending information provides us with information about the things we are most interested in. However, in targeting information by using user profiling, “algorithmic targeting plays a special role in epistemic worldmaking, as it reinforces beliefs that users might already be sympathetic or susceptible to, and which appear “normal” within the epistemic worlds into which they have been sorted” (Stewart, et al., 2022: 9). This is particularly a concern for democracy if the information which is targeted towards users is misinformation, or disinformation.

Lynch (2017) makes a distinction between targeted advertising (advertising and post recommendations which are targeted using user profiles, but then may be shared or are at least discoverable by those not targeted), and dark advertising (advertises which are only shown to users part of highly “specific demographic parameters”. Some warn of the dangers of dark advertising, such as the lack of transparency, accountability, and the use of personal data (Lynch, 2017; Saunders, 2020; Trott, et al., 2021). Dark advertising is particularly pernicious when related to political campaigns and the access some citizens may have to information that others do not. These concerns go beyond the concerns we may have about traditional advertising campaigns for two reasons: it can occur “in the dark”, and different messages can be sent to different groups (Saunders, 2020: 75). This is something that has already been seen by the likes of the Cambridge Analytica scandal and their use of Facebook adverts in the Brexit vote, and the 2016 US election (Confessore, 2018; Manheim and Kaplan, 2019: 109). Theorists have described the rise of this phenomena as “the rise of the weaponized AI propaganda machine” (Anderson and Horvath, 2017).

Saunders (2020: 77) outlines five reasons dark advertising is a threat to democracy. Dark advertisements:

1. Are not part of the national conversation
2. Are difficult for the political media to track

3. Undermine the marketplace of ideas
4. Cannot be challenged or fact-checked
5. Cause long-term issues, such as disenfranchisement and polarisation

(Saunders, 2020: 77)

Dark advertising therefore undermines the equality of access to information needed for citizens to make informed voting decisions, and to be informed about issues in the first place. As Trott, Li, Fordyce, and Andrejevic (2021: 762-763) note, adverts have the power to shape our values and attitudes, even if this is not their primary aim. Moreover, dark advertising can focus debates on more divisive issues, for example immigration or welfare (Saunders, 2020: 76-77). These issues have traditionally been particularly mobilising for voters, and coupled with the inability to fact-check or challenge their claims, dark advertising poses a particularly important threat both in terms of polarisation of views and access to information. This is particularly harmful to democratic deliberation and civic participation. We will return to these further problems of algorithmic targeting in sections 2.3.1 and 2.4.1.

2.1.2 Decision-Making

Another way that the use of personal data and user profiling may threaten equality is through their use in decision-making. This section outlines two stages within AI-assisted decision-making where bias and discrimination may occur: in the collection and analysis of personal data to create user profiles, and in the use of user profiles in automated decision-making.

2.1.2.1 Bias and Discrimination in User Profiling

User profiling of course relies heavily on the generations and collection of personal data both by humans, and by systems created by humans (Ntoutsi, et al., 2020: 3). As such, bias and discrimination may arise in many different aspects such as the targeting hypotheses used to train AI algorithms, encoding of data, and problems with representativeness of data. Bias can come in many forms and may occur at different stages of the data collection and analysis process. Some types of bias include selection bias (including self-selection, and exclusion bias), information bias (i.e., misinformation, and regression to the mean), or confounding (Delgado-Rodriguez & Llorca, 2004). Bias is a particular issue for the use of user profiling since the data used to design user profiles may be inaccurate, and this may lead to bias and discrimination when ADM uses these user profiles in its decision-making.

In terms of the hypotheses used to define the goal for an AI-assisted algorithm, when designing an AI model, businesses or institutions must translate their broader goal (for example to market a product at people who are likely to buy their product) into inputs, criteria, and labels that can be understood by an AI system (Roselli, et al., 2019). Roselli, Matthews and Talagala (2019) note that in doing so, corporations or institutions may use information such as historical data (for example information about those who have previously bought similar products), or “surrogate data” (for example, a credit score as a source of data about a person's

reliability rather than a letter of recommendation). These can introduce bias in two ways. The first is that the data used to train the AI model may not be reflective of the data the model is eventually used upon. This may result in predictions being made that do not accurately relate to those whom the system should be targeting, thus excluding people because of historical bias. The second, is that the use of surrogate data results in information loss, which may introduce bias also if the information that has been excluded was important in some way.

Existing bias may also be imported into data encoding through the use of historical data or surrogate data. Importantly, this may be the case even if sensitive personal data is not present since the use of redundant encodings (other features that are correlated with the sensitive data) still exist (Ntousti, et al., 2020: 3). For example, certain neighbourhoods or areas may be associated with a certain demographic (Roselli, et al., 2019; Ntousti, et al., 2020: 4). This is likely the result of influences, causations, and correlations between data not being properly understood.

The data used within user profiles may also not be truly representative of either individuals, or demographic groups. For example, data may have been manipulated, mislabelled, mismatched, unlearned, or unseen (Roselli, et al., 2019). When these problems within the data themselves coincide with existing bias and discrimination in society against these certain groups, this can lead to discriminatory decisions (Calders & Žliobaitė, 2013: 53). This is also a problem on the bigger scale, since big data may over or under represent certain groups if the datasets have been created without sufficient attention to who is included (Ntousti, et al., 2020: 4). We return to this discussion in Module E when discussing the use of AI and ADM in criminal law.

2.1.2.2 Bias and Discrimination in Automated Decision-Making

AI systems are often trained on existing data sets, which may contain biases or reflect historical and structural inequalities that affect marginalised groups in society (O'Neill 2016, Eubanks 2018). As a result, AI systems may reproduce or amplify these biases and inequalities in their outputs, leading to discriminatory decisions that compromise the principle of equal treatment in democratic societies (FRA 2020; 2022). This is especially problematic when AI systems are used in public services that have a direct impact on people's lives and rights, such as social welfare, policing, judicial system, health care, and banking. Several examples of such cases have been documented in the literature, such as the COMPAS system in the US that was found to be biased against African-American defendants in predicting recidivism rates (Angwin et al. 2016), and the SyRI system in the Netherlands that was used to detect fraud in social benefits and was accused of discriminating against low-income and immigrant households (Bekker 2021). To address such issues, more technical work within the field of machine learning and algorithmic fairness has blossomed, in order to develop methods and metrics to quantify and mitigate the potential biases of AI systems towards different groups of people (Ntousti et al. 2020; Mehrabi et al. 2021). Yet, many scholars note that biases of AI systems are socio-technical issues that depend on societal context and cannot merely be reduced to technical fairness metrics or fixes (Selbst et al. 2019).

2.2 Privacy

Privacy is of both intrinsic and instrumental importance to democracy.⁴ For example, for deliberation to take place citizens must be afforded a degree of autonomy (Boehme-Neßler, 2016: 227-228). As Boehme-Neßler (206: 227-228) notes, privacy is inextricably linked to autonomy because it is only through an element of privacy that citizens can “develop, learn and then exercise autonomy”.⁵ Without privacy, citizens may for example feel that their actions are over scrutinised, or prescribed in some way. Moreover, citizens’ actions and behaviour may change if they feel they have not been afforded adequate privacy.

The use of personal data and user profiling by both institutions and business arguably infringes upon this democratic right to privacy. For one, it is now nearly impossible to use the internet or other knowledge technologies without leaving some kind of data trail. For example, it was predicted that by the end of 2023 there would be 43 billion devices connected to the Internet of Things (IoT) (Marr, 2022). The use of personal data and user profiling is of particular concern for the privacy of citizens because of the ways that behaviour and action can be predicted. We will return to this in Module E when discussing the way that AI and big data can resist individual freedom of speech and action.

Conceptions of personal data often focus on ownership rights (Hazel, 2020; Hummel, et al., 2020; Janeček, 2018). However, the expansion of big data and the IoT has shifted the focus from data collection to data processing and analysis and this has provided some criticism of a purely ownership-based model of data privacy (Mai, 2016: 194-197). Given that data ownership can be relational - more than one person or institution can ‘own’ this data, for example both yourself and the business you frequent own the data on your shopping habits - ownership alone does not seem to explain our privacy protection concerns (Mai, 2016: 196). Floridi (2005: 195) outlines an ontological interpretation of personal data; it is not that you own your personal data, but rather your personal data constitutively belongs to you - it *is* you. This interpretation goes some way in helping us to understand why the use of personal data in user profiling and ADM may be an infringement of privacy.

Another way to understand our privacy concerns from the use of AI and big data is from the view of the harm a lack of privacy can cause. Prosser (cited in Manheim and Kaplan, 2019: 117) outlines four distinct harms that arise from the violation of privacy: “1) intrusion upon seclusion or solitude, or into private affairs; 2) public disclosure of embarrassing private facts; 3) false light publicity; and 4) appropriation of name or likeness”. These harms are directly related to data privacy in that the collection, processing, and analysis of personal data can contribute to these harms directly and indirectly. Most obviously, the collection of personal data can directly infringe upon a person’s private affairs, or insecure storage of personal data can lead to data leaks. This section explores two main emerging privacy concerns about the use of personal data and user profiling: the way that profiling itself can infringe upon privacy, and the use and storage of training data in generative AI systems.

⁴ Instrumental and intrinsic reasons to value democracy are discussed in section 1.3.

⁵ Relatedly, privacy is also important for certain forms of civil disobedience, as discussed in module E.

2.2.1 Profiling as an Infringement on Privacy

Due to the sensitivity of personal data, it follows that we believe individuals should have some privacy rights, even if these are not grounded in ‘ownership’ of data. As a consequence, it follows that institutions, businesses and corporations have a corresponding duty to respect this right. The predictive power of some AI-algorithms, ADM and user profiling however presents a further issue that previous concerns about big data did not. It is not only that datasets together can help to glean information about individuals and collectives, but that *new information* can be generated from the analysis of this data. For an anecdotal example, consider the father who complained to US store Target for sending his daughter coupons for maternity clothes (Mai, 2016: 192). However, it transpired that previous buying history of the daughter produced a “pregnancy prediction score” and which saw Target ‘knowing’ she was pregnant before anyone else (Duhigg, 2012; Mai, 2016: 192). As Mai (2016: 199) notes, the advent of big data, and we believe also the use of user profiling and ADM, has caused us to rethink privacy. The ‘datafication’ of privacy has arguably shifted the focus away from privacy concerns about data collection, and towards concerns about data analysis and processing (Mai, 2016: 199). One such concern is the way that user profiling can generate information, like in the case above. This is a threat to privacy because things may be understood about a ‘data subject’ even without them giving this information, whether knowingly or not, to the data controller. Moreover, if the information determined from user profiling is incorrect, this nonetheless counts as an infringement of privacy.

Some solutions have been proposed to protect the privacy of users whilst still harnessing the benefits of big data and machine learning techniques (Khalid, et al., 2023; Oseni, et al., 2021). These solutions often rest upon the idea that data ‘capture’ is never neutral or passive but is “always socio-technical in nature” and that the way that technology captures our data affects the way we interact with it (Agre, 1994: 112). Mai’s (2016: 198) datafication model of privacy recognises this and argues that we must place focus on “facts the entities have produced about people”, not just those they have collected, to truly understand the risks to privacy. This is especially important for the use of user profiling.

2.2.2 Generative AI and Personal Data

Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs), large language models (LLMs) such as OpenAI’s ChatGPT, or Google’s Bard utilise user data for training purposes.⁶ This poses two main concerns for the privacy of such data: the first is a concern about what data is collected and how it is used, and the second concerns how safe the data is stored.

Concerning the training data used for generative AI systems, web scraping is often used. For example, Chat GPT-3.5 was trained on 300 billion words of writing from the internet (Hughes, 2023). This training data may therefore inevitably include some personal data. Moreover, to improve the accuracy and performance of LLMs, they also often use the user data and prompts inputted. This poses a risk to privacy of those whose personal data has made its way into training data, either through web scraping or via information users have

⁶ It is important to note that Chat GPT 4 allows for users to opt out of their data being used for training purposes (Gupta, et al., 2023: 80242).

inputted into the system. First, many users may not be aware that the data they input into generative AI systems may be used in this way. Second, the question arises about the safe storage of such data and who has access to it. This is a particular problem for LLMs as this personal data may be ‘generated’ into an answer given to other users. This may also be used for nefarious purposes. There have already been instances of this, with users being able to bypass safety systems and access training data within Chat GPT (Gupta, et al., 2023: 80242).

2.3 Transparency and Accountability

Transparency and accountability are fundamental concerns when we place our trust both in other people, and in technology. This is of particular importance in democracies because of the ways knowledge technologies intersect with civic participation. This section outlines two risks involved in the reliance on AI systems: transparency and accountability for data use, and transparency and accountability in decision-making by ADM and AI systems.

2.3.1 Considerations for Data Use

As discussed previously in section 2.2, personal data use is a fundamental privacy issue. With this however comes the responsibility to adequately protect this data. Personal data needs to be protected because of privacy concerns. This means not only concerns about *who* has access to *what* data, but for what *purpose*, and *why*. As discussed throughout this module, because of the interest private companies have in big data - data is a form of currency after all - citizens need to be able to trust that their data is only being used in the ways described by companies. As will be discussed in section 3 on regulation of AI and big data, GDPR has done much to bring these discussions to the fore, not just in Europe but worldwide. Whilst regulation like this can provide a good baseline of transparency, and arguably more importantly accountability, in the use of personal data, compliance with the law is not the be all and end all of ethical behaviour.

When things go wrong however, for example data leaks caused by human error, accountability for these mistakes is important. It has been suggested that the use of AI and ADM may in fact reduce data breach costs by containing them faster (Lehmann and Durfee, 2023). Whilst this may be positive from a data safety standpoint, problems with the transparency and accountability of ADM brings with it questions about whether we can fully understand the way that ADM makes decisions, and who is accountable if these decisions are wrong.

Moreover, in the context of democracy, the use of big data poses an interesting problem for accountability - decision-making is no longer theory based, instead there has been an epistemological shift towards data-led decisions (Kempeneer, 2021: 3). This is a problem for accountability and transparency, not only because of black-box thinking from AI and ADM, but because theory is seen to be necessary for understanding ‘*why*’ - correlation is not the full picture (Kempeneer, 2021: 3).

2.3.2 Black Box Decision-Making

AI systems are often complex and opaque, making it hard for users and affected parties to understand and contest their logic and outcomes. This can prevent public oversight and accountability of the impact of AI systems on democratic processes and values. The black box nature of automated decision-making systems can also undermine trust and confidence in democratic institutions and authorities. To address this issue, legal and ethical frameworks are needed to ensure that AI systems are transparent and accountable, and that people have the right to know and challenge the decisions that affect them. One such framework is the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which arguably grants people the right not to be subject to a decision based solely on automated processing, as well as the right to obtain an explanation of the decision, although these are contested issues (Wachter, Mittelstadt & Floridi 2017; Kaminski 2019). However, transparency and accountability are not straightforward concepts, and may vary depending on the context and implications of a given AI system. Novelli, Taddeo & Floridi (2023) define algorithmic accountability in terms of answerability that requires authority recognition, interrogation and limitation of power. Furthermore, policymakers may utilise accountability either proactively or reactively in governing AI, depending on whether it targets compliance, oversight, or enforcement.

This black-box nature means we cannot be fully aware of how an AI is achieving a goal (Shaw, 2019: 2). By implementing AI into democratic decision making in any capacity we cannot be sure if it is using discriminatory methods to reach its goals (Manheim and Kaplan, 2019: 155). Often it is taken that AI's reliance on data makes it impartial. However, some AI used to advise courts in the US on the likelihood of recidivism have been found to actually do the opposite, being almost twice as likely to suggest that a black defendant is likely to repeat a crime than white defendants (Angwin et al, 2016; Manheim and Kaplan, 2019: 157). More broadly, owing to issues mentioned in section 2.2 such as initial input data being biased, or creator biases, it seems often it is the case that AI systems falsely equate correlations with causations in their decision making (Sherman, 2018). Thus, increased implementation may lead to greater inequality (Shorey and Howard, 2018: 5033).

'Transparent algorithms' and explainable AI are often cited as a potential solution to some forms of black-box thinking. And these may be valuable tools for institutions to be seen to be fair and legitimate (Vredenburg, 2022: 78). These are discussed in section 3.1 when discussing how tech firms should, or should not be, regulated. A related solution is also ensuring human input and oversight over decision-making (Sartori and Theodorou, 2022: 4). This can come in many forms, such as 'human in the loop' (Sartori and Theodorou, 2022: 4; Zanzotto, 2019).

2.4 Participation

Public deliberation in its varying forms makes clear the preferences of the citizens of a society. This is important because AI and big data might seriously alter the ways in which deliberation can take place. We value public deliberation within democracies both instrumentally and intrinsically. Some instrumental reasons to value public deliberation include the development of better laws, those laws being publicly justified, and it can also improve the character of citizens, for example by increasing their autonomy or rationality (Christiano, 1997: 214). Intrinsically, the process of public deliberation may be seen as valuable

because it embodies a mutual respect among citizens. Political debate is centred around deliberation on the public good, not based on self or group interests. When parties deliberate, weight should only be given to arguments which openly appeal to the public good (Rawls, 2004). Interestingly, the reasons we value public deliberation overlap with the reasons we value democracy outlined in 1.3.

This section outlines the ways in which civic participation and public deliberation may be undermined or threatened by the use of personal data and user profiling. The ways that AI and big data may alter democratic procedures or erode the public sphere will be explored.

2.4.1 Potential to Alter Democratic Procedures

AI systems can influence, shape, or even replace human choices and actions, thereby undermining human autonomy and judgement in democratic decision-making. For instance, some scholars have warned of the risk of ‘algocracy’, a situation where increasing decision-making authority is given to AI systems, constraining and limiting opportunities for human participation and legitimacy of political decisions (Danaher 2016; Sætra 2020). Moreover, AI systems can diminish the epistemic agency of citizens, that is, their ability to acquire, evaluate, and communicate information, which is essential for a well-functioning democracy (Coeckelbergh 2023). To prevent or reduce the negative impacts of AI on human autonomy and judgement, several measures can be taken at different levels of design, implementation, and governance. Some of these measures are: designing AI systems that respect and support human autonomy, rather than hinder or manipulate it (Laitinen & Sahlgren 2021); ensuring that human users and stakeholders are informed and aware of the capabilities, limitations, and potential biases of AI systems, and that they can exercise meaningful control and oversight over them (Verbeek 2011; Calvo et al. 2020).

There are several ways that democracy’s ability to make good laws could be improved by the presence of AI and big data. One way of looking at this is to ask how democratic systems could be adapted to improve decision making. These include wiki democracy, data democracy, and AI democracy. We take each of these in turn and explain how they may both provide an opportunity for, and a threat to, democratic participation.

There are large sources of information that can be edited by anyone, such as Wikipedia: this method for developing large platforms which anyone can contribute is called ‘open-source production’ (Noveck, 2009; Watkins, et al., 2016). Using a common platform, all citizens could contribute towards the production of policies and legislation (Susskind, 2018: 243). The main advantage of this regarding policy making is that large groups of individuals are more likely to come to correct conclusions.⁷ A wiki democracy would be a form of open-source policy making, thus offering any individual with the ability to access it the ability to directly influence laws and policy decisions (Susskind, 2018: 242).

However, there are several issues with this. First, there may still exist a lack of motivation to participate. Regular democratic procedures are often subject to low voter turnout. In part this is because people are either too busy, or care too little (Cassidy, 2022). It stands to reason that asking them to become an active participant in making laws would yield even lower results (Susskind, 2018: 245). Further, very few people would be able to edit either code or laws. In effect, only those with the knowhow would be able to edit the

⁷ This is similar to the claim of Condorcet’s Jury Theorem as discussed in section 1.3 (Condorcet, 1785).

laws, resulting in a more epistocratic system (Susskind, 2018: 245). Finally, in simple terms, deliberation does not always equate to decision making. Assuming people were both willing and able to do this, the ability to deliberate in continually altering the law would result in no definite decisions ever being made (Durning, 2004; Lanier, 2014: 55-60). It would therefore be highly impractical since its fluidity would limit individuals' awareness of the law. This may however be solved through reasonable constraints set out to limit the extent to which policy could be open sourced.

Relatedly, the idea of a data democracy may be seen as a viable supplementation to our existing democratic processes. Whilst many decisions require consideration by individuals, we now have a wealth of data on some particular issues (Susskind, 2018: 247). Many decisions, such as where best to distribute funds to ensure long term prosperity could be made by AI analysing data to optimise decision making (Harari, 2016: 327-342). This reliance on data could offer a degree of impartiality; removing human bias from decision making (Bohannon, 2017; Manheim and Kaplan, 2019: 155).

However, data may be applied impartially, and as we have outlined throughout this module, there is no way of guaranteeing the data itself is of a suitable standard to make truly good decisions (Susskind: 2018: 248). We may also believe that a data democracy lacks legitimacy since neither citizens, nor their representatives have the power to make decisions (though this may be resolved through some veto power).

The concept of an AI democracy has many different ways it could be implemented, for example AI advisors or AI voter delegates. Essentially, we could use algorithms individually to improve our own decision-making ability (Susskind, 2018: 251). AI Advisors could perform an advisory function in predicting how we should vote. Perhaps you enter in information about yourself (creating your user profile for yourself by entering personal data) then the AI builds a profile of you, advising you on which way would be the best way for you to vote (Mols, et al, 2022).

Alternatively, AI voter delegates, using an algorithm and user profiling, could vote on our behalf for designated issues. This could be done frequently with regard to smaller pieces of legislation (Harari, 2016: 340). These systems would likely run into issues faced prior, namely, we cannot be sure how these AI come to their decisions, or if they have been created in such a way as to bias them. They could also potentially be hacked, which could severely threaten democracy (Manheim and Kaplan, 2019: 134 – 138; Susskind, 2018: 253).

These uses of AI could be justified in regard to enhancing equality on egalitarian grounds. Many people owing to their circumstances have neither the time or the ability to 'do themselves justice' and make an informed decision on who they should vote for. If an AI could do this for them (or advise them to vote a certain way) this could better accommodate the disadvantaged since many people lack the time to do a thorough investigation into all material facts. It could also be used to help those who lack the ability to understand the material even if they had all the facts. This would not only benefit laypersons with a general lack of expertise in politics, but also those with severe mental disabilities, or those suffering from long term illness such as Alzheimer's, or those in comas. Moreover, the use of AI in this way may in some sense prevent misdirection. After the 2016 referendum on Brexit, some polls showed that near a quarter of 'leave' voters felt that they had been misled (Farand, 2017). It is now predicted that if the referendum was retaken, remain would have won, and that the misinformation offered by the vote leave campaign was a significant factor in the actual outcome. With this example in mind, if an AI system tailored to each individual acted as an impartial advisor,

it may prevent decisions being made against the interests of the individuals making said decisions as a result of some misinformation. The AI knows what is important to that person and may explain why that person should vote a particular way.

However, as discussed in section 2.3.2, AI algorithms can be seen as a ‘black box’, since humans cannot be fully aware of how an AI is achieving a goal (Shaw, 2019: 2). By implementing AI into democratic decision making in any capacity we cannot be sure if it is using discriminatory methods to reach its goals (Manheim and Kaplan, 2019: 155). Owing to issues such as initial input data being biased, or creator biases, it seems often it is the case that AI falsely equates correlations with causations in decision making (Sherman, 2018). Thus, increased implementation may lead to greater inequality (Shorey and Howard, 2018: 5033).

2.4.2 Erosion of the Public Sphere

AI has become an integral part of the public sphere, the arena of discursive interaction where citizens form and express their opinions on matters of common concern. However, the increasing reliance on AI-driven applications by media platforms and political actors influences the quality and diversity of information accessible to citizens with consequences for democratic deliberation. According to Jungherr (2023), AI can affect democracy in various ways, such as influencing the conditions and opportunities for self-rule, the institution of elections, and the competition between democratic and autocratic regimes. Moreover, Jungherr and Schroeder (2023) argue that AI can also impact the public sphere itself, by shaping the information environment and the content that citizens encounter and share online. Algorithms that filter, rank, recommend, or generate content can create echo chambers, polarisation, misinformation, or propaganda that undermine democratic deliberation and the formation of publics and counterpublics. In particular Jungherr and Schroeder argue that AI is likely to strengthen the intermediary structures of the public arena, hide challenges to the political status quo and fortify control by gatekeepers.

3 Regulating the Use of Personal Data and User Profiling

Floridi (2018) offers a useful distinction between hard and soft ethics. “Hard ethics” encompasses the “values, rights, duties and responsibilities” discussed when formulating regulation (Floridi, 2018: 4). “Soft ethics” in contrast, discusses the same values, rights, duties, and responsibilities not from a regulation point of view, but from a post-compliance angle - i.e., what should be done once existing regulation has been obeyed (Floridi, 2018: 4). Whilst much of what has been discussed within this module so far may reasonably be seen as a form of soft ethics, it is important to understand the evolving sphere of hard ethics as related to AI and big data. In what follows, we outline some ways that have been considered in the literature as methods to regulate the technology space including structural regulation and transparent algorithms, the current concentration of power to AI companies, and existing and emerging regulation. In later versions of this module, we will explore whether regulation really does harm innovation, and ways in which this can either be dispelled, or mitigated against.

3.1 How Should Tech Firms Be Regulated?

Companies have such sway over how and what is up for public deliberation, and so the algorithms that govern these online spaces should be constrained to sufficiently account for these public interests (Susskind, 2018: 350).⁸ Perhaps the easiest way of returning control of a public good to the people would be nationalisation of AI companies. However, this also affords the government considerable power, to tailor public discourse to their interests (Susskind, 2018: 350). As such, nationalisation may lead to the aforementioned “digital gerrymandering” (Zittrain, 2014).

In lieu of these issues, some have suggested that companies be treated like public utilities and regulated in such a way as to protect the public interest (Cohen, 2016: 378 – 382; Rahman, 2018). In this way, many have argued in favour of ‘net neutrality’ – that companies for example cannot change the speed of internet connectivity, or limit access to content against their interests (Lanier, 2014). There are however some important differences between public utilities and technology companies. Utility companies are regulated because they control a public good (electricity etc), and whilst technology companies do this too, they uniquely have political power over who sees what.⁹ As such, to compare them to utilities seems insufficient (Susskind, 2018: 157). Moreover, companies can be just as unjust and corrupt as governments, perhaps even more so, as such, why should we trust them to run these utilities over the government (Pasquale, 2017).

Moreover, since political power is associated with the ownership of online forums (and the algorithms that govern them), we might want to restrict how much of a forum (or how many forums) can be owned by one individual or company. In essence, by doing this we accept that some platforms will advantage some ideologies, but in allowing for no one company to monopolise this, we could adequately protect deliberation of all sorts (Susskind, 2018: 358). This form of structural regulation however may actually further stand to polarise political discourse online, with each platform becoming its own echo chamber.

If traditional regulation cannot provide all the answers, then, the notion of transparent algorithms may be a useful element in a package of regulation. If all data usage and algorithms are clearly displayed in a manner which is understandable to the layman, we could greater trust these to govern our public platforms (Granka, 2010: 365; Manheim and Kaplan, 2019: 170; Susskind, 2018: 354). However, tech companies of course have private interests and may not be keen to display their information to their competitors. X (formerly Twitter) however have done this to a certain extent by open-sourcing their recommendation algorithm for example (Twitter, 2023a; Twitter 2023b). However, this move has been criticised due to mistakes, incomplete code, and underlying code being completely missing (Vaughan-Nichols, 2023). Open-source models will be further discussed in section 3.2.3.

One final notion to explore is the idea that technology itself can be democratised to mitigate some of the risks. Whilst it is possible to further limit the power of private firms to control deliberation, we could also incorporate democracy itself into technology (Susskind: 2018: 359). For example, we can imagine free platforms where anyone can modify code, or methods of scrutiny that could be applied to the creators of public forums before they are made available to the public.

⁸ This is further discussed in section 3.2.

⁹ This is explored in Module E.

3.2 Concentration of Power to AI Companies

One of the major challenges of governing artificial intelligence (AI) is the concentration of power to AI companies that develop and deploy AI systems. This is especially so when privately developed AI systems are integrated into public societal infrastructure, such as health, education, transportation, and communication. This integration threatens to give these actors disproportionate influence over the public arena, where society communicates and forms opinions (Jungherr & Schroeder 2023). Moreover, this integration limits the public scrutiny and democratic participation in the development and use of AI systems, as they become less visible and assessable (Maham & Küspert 2023). Therefore, some scholars have argued that a greater antimonopoly approach to governance is needed to prevent the AI oligopoly from abusing its power and harming the economic, social, and political interests of the public (Ganesh & Narechania 2023). An anti-monopoly approach would entail using various tools, such as industrial policy, network and platform regulation, public options, and cooperative governance, to shape the market structure and facilitate competition and innovation in the AI sector.

AI can undermine democracy also through concentration of power to actors which lack democratic accountability. Below we present a typology that is divided into (3.2.1) direct risks and (3.2.2) structural and systemic risks, which especially relate concentration of power.

3.2.1 Direct Risks Connected to AI Systems and Models Themselves, Especially in Decision-Making and Electoral Contexts

Automated decision-making can unintentionally violate the rights and interests of citizens in various domains, raising issues of bias, transparency and accountability. AI can also be used to target, persuade, or manipulate voters through personalization, microtargeting, or undermining integrity of electoral democracy.

Unintentional risks in automated decision-making (see above):

- Algorithmic bias and discrimination
- Opaqueness and intransparency of AI models
- Misalignment and safety risks of advanced models

Intentional misuse in politics:

- Disinformation and deep fakes
- Surveillance, profiling and privacy considerations
- Campaign and electoral manipulation

3.2.2 Structural and Systemic Risks to Democratic Participation

Structural risks concern how the AI systems interact with larger social, political, and economic forces. This includes whose voice is heard and who holds the power in society. Moreover, AI influences the quality and diversity of information that citizens receive through algorithms that filter, rank, recommend, or generate content. This can create distrust and polarisation that undermines democratic deliberation and public opinion formation.

- Centralisation of power to few private companies given the prohibitive compute, training and data requirements of AI models versus states.
- Lack of democratic oversight and alignment of AI with the popular will, especially with the geopolitical and national securitisation of AI.
- Diminishing epistemic agency of citizens essential to democratic public sphere and representation due to reliance on AI.
- Rise of inequality through AI's impacts on labour market and economy, displacement and exploitation of workers.
- Societal and political distrust if personalised AI systems violate rights and liberties of citizens as part of public services.

3.2.3 The Question of Open-Source AI Models

Open-source models are closely related to the debate about centralisation of power through AI. On the one hand, open-source AI models can foster openness, competition and pluralism, which are essential pillars of democracies. On the other hand, such models can also create security risks, such as the proliferation of disinformation and deepfakes, that can undermine the quality and integrity of democratic deliberation and decision-making (Hintersdorf et al. 2023). Therefore, some scholars and policymakers have argued that access to advanced open-source AI models should be limited or regulated, for instance by imposing licensing requirements on AI developers and users (Seger et al. 2023). However, this approach may entail a trade-off between security and openness, as it could result in the concentration of power and influence to a few AI labs or companies, which are not accountable or transparent to the public. Moreover, it could stifle innovation and diversity in the AI field and create barriers for smaller or marginalised actors to participate and benefit from AI applications. Some also argue that open-source in the context of AI does not carry the usual benefits of democratisation given the massive computational resources required to build and deploy AI at scale, and accordingly the term has become co-opted by large technology companies such as OpenAI or Meta (Widder, West & Whittaker 2023). In any case, the regulation of frontier AI models in the interest of safety and democracy can still violate principles of open societies and serve to concentrate power on AI companies. Thus, the question of how to balance the security and openness of AI models in democratic societies is a complex and urgent one, that requires careful consideration of the potential impacts and implications of more open or closed model releases going forward. Such discussions have already started to take shape, for example during the final stages of the AI Act trilogues (Council of the EU, 2023).

3.3 Current Regulatory Frameworks

3.3.1 Existing and Emerging Policies

The evolving EU digital policy has already by 2023 been through three development phases. The gradual progress has move towards more robust legislation through 1) the initial era of ethics principles and guidelines (2017-2019); 2) preliminary policy and governance on more specific domains, e.g. NIST framework (2020-2022); to reach 3) actual policies and legislation (2023). An important culmination point of this in Nov/Dec 2023 is the set of agreements and declarations, which seek to govern and address the risks and potential of AI in different contexts, including the agreement on AI Act, the US Executive Order, the G7 Hiroshima agreement, and the Bletchley Declaration. Most importantly, this has meant a shift in discourse to safety and security of GPAI systems. As is seen in the former discursive shifts towards securitisation, this shift includes a risk of narrowing down the problem to the perspective of security and may result in overlooking broader angles such as AI ethics and democracy. This is important not only from the perspective of the drafting and scope of future policy and legislation, but also because the next challenge will be the actual implementation and enforcement of this regulation.

Evolving AI policy is emerging simultaneously at different governance levels. The multilateral global governance initiatives include Recommendation on the Ethics of Artificial Intelligence published by UNESCO (2022), AI principles by OECD (2019), and The Global Partnership for Artificial Intelligence (GPAI, 2021) building on the OECD recommendations on AI. Furthermore, collaboration has emerged also among the G7 Hiroshima AI process Comprehensive Policy Framework (European Commission, 2023a) and in the context of the EU/US bilateral cooperation.

The supra-national level legislation at the EU level, such as the AI Act, the AI Liability Directive, Digital Service Act and the Digital Markets Act, will be applied at the national level. Other national level initiatives include the US Executive Order published in October 2023, and the UK pro-innovation approach to AI. Also, China, India and Latin America have taken stances in recognising the societal and political implications of AI in their own ways. In China, the government has published a Position Paper of the People's Republic of China on Strengthening Ethical Governance of Artificial Intelligence (AI) (Ministry of Foreign Affairs of the People's Republic of China, 2022). India on the other hand has adopted an intensely growth and innovation-oriented approach without developing a robust AI regulation (NITI Aayog, 2018). Most recently, the Economic Commission for Latin America and the Caribbean (ECLAC) launched The first Latin American AI Index, which forms a stepping stone towards further adoption and collaboration on AI in the region (ECLAC, 2023).

In addition to governments and international organisations, also the industry level has pushed their own initiatives. These include Partnership on AI (2024), the EU driven AI Pact (European Commission, 2023b) and the voluntary AI commitments in the US (The White House, 2023b). Still, among the manifold openings in the field, the EU has managed to position itself as the regulatory leader on digital and AI policies, hoping to leverage the single market Brussels effect (Bradford 2020), although now faces catch-up by other countries. The AI Act is based on a new legislative framework, digital markets and product legislation unlike fundamental rights-oriented GDPR. The risk-based approach carries both benefits and vices (Kaminski 2023).

Some of the relevant questions for future regulatory discussions include:

- To what extent is the use case product legislation and risk-based approach enshrined in the AI Act fit for general-purpose AI systems?
- Should there be restrictions on the development of increasingly larger models? Are quantitative thresholds such as 10^{25} FLOPs of compute power the right tool?
- How can we balance technical expertise with effective democratic control in AI regulation; e.g. civil society perspective in standard-setting?
- What should be the role of citizen participation and NGOs in AI governance?
- Can regulation that focuses on individual rights uphold and safeguard collective democratic principles and communicative norms?
- To what extent is the proposed regulation and its enforcement enough (e.g. GDPR vs use of copyrighted data in LLMs) or are new institutions needed?

The current EU approach to AI regulation faces several challenges and limitations that need to be addressed. One of the main issues is the difficulty in enforcing the existing and proposed rules, due to the unsuitability of product legislation for AI and the lack of resources for the regulatory and enforcement agencies of AI. Another challenge is the compatibility of the EU approach with the collective bargaining and co-determination models that are prevalent in some member states. How can the EU ensure that workers are adequately involved in the governance of AI systems that affect their work environment and conditions? A third issue is the power relations and liability between the providers and the users of general-purpose AI systems. The EU approach seems to be unclear or reluctant to assign liability to the providers of AI systems, which may create an imbalance of power and responsibility between them and the users or deployers of the systems. Finally, the sustainability and material footprints of AI systems are often overlooked in the EU approach, despite it being a potentially important leverage.

3.3.2 Underlying Democratic Implications of Policy and Regulatory Approaches

The regulation of AI is a complex and contested issue that involves multiple actors, interests, and values. The policy and regulatory approaches to AI have underlying democratic implications that need to be critically examined. Smuha (2021) argues that the global landscape of AI regulation has shifted from a 'Race to AI' to a 'Race to AI Regulation', as different actors and regions compete to set the norms and standards for AI development and deployment. However, the drivers and motivations behind AI regulation are not homogeneous or neutral, but rather reflect the interests and values of different stakeholders from a critical political economy perspective (Regine 2023). First, AI regulation can be seen as a normative project of applied ethics, aiming to ensure that AI is aligned with human dignity and rights. Second, it can also be seen as a technocratic rational choice endeavour, balancing between the promotion of innovation and the mitigation of ethical risks. Thirdly, AI regulation can be influenced by regulatory capture by industry, which may seek to shape the rules in their favour or avoid strict oversight. Finally, AI regulation can be driven by the state

competition perspective, which views AI as a strategic asset and a source of geopolitical power.

One way to AI regulation is to examine the imaginaries and narratives that shape the public and policy discourse on it. Bareis and Katzenbach (2022) argue that national AI strategies are a form of co-shaping AI development and deployment, as they offer imaginaries, allocate resources, and set rules. However, they also show that the imaginaries and narratives of AI regulation differ significantly across countries, reflecting their cultural, political, and economic contexts. Another way to approach this issue is to explore the different meanings and goals of democratising AI, which is often invoked as a desirable aim. Seger, Ovadya, Siddarth et al. (2023) identify four kinds of AI democratisation that are commonly discussed: the democratisation of AI use, development, profits, and governance. They also discuss the methods and challenges of achieving each form of democratisation and highlight the need for the democratisation of AI governance as a way to navigate trade-offs and risks.

A final, critical approach to the values behind AI governance is to analyse the convergence and divergence of AI ethics principles and guidelines, which are meant to provide normative guidance for AI design and use. Corrêa et al. (2023) find that there is a substantial convergence of AI ethics principles and guidelines across the world, but also note that democratic values are interpreted differently depending on the context and perspective. They suggest that AI ethics principles and guidelines should be complemented by more concrete and contextualised mechanisms and practices. Similarly, Jobin, Ienca and Vayena (2019) and Hagendorff (2020) provide comprehensive evaluations of AI ethics principles and guidelines and point out the gaps and limitations of these documents. They call for more clarity, consistency, and operationalization of AI ethics principles and guidelines, as well as more stakeholder involvement and accountability.

3.3.3 Effective Democratic Control in AI Regulation

One of the main challenges for democratic AI governance is the capacity to implement and enforce the regulation, which requires adequate resources, expertise, and coordination among the relevant authorities. The EU has proposed to establish an European AI Office to oversee and support the application of the AI Act. However, the AI Office may face difficulties in ensuring compliance and accountability of AI providers and users, especially in cases of high-risk AI systems that pose serious threats to public goods. Another challenge is the standard setting process, which is crucial for defining the technical requirements and specifications for AI systems. The AI Act is likely to rely on non-transparent industrial standard-setting bodies, such as CEN-CENELEC, which lack civil society representation and may be influenced by the interests of the AI industry (Ada Lovelace Institute 2023). This may undermine the legitimacy and inclusiveness of the standards, as well as the alignment of AI systems with democratic values and principles.

One opportunity is to promote deliberative processes and mini-publics in AI governance, which refer to the involvement of diverse and informed citizens in decision-making. Deliberative democracy and mini-publics can enhance the quality and legitimacy of AI governance, by fostering legitimacy and public acceptance as well as by providing critical and constructive feedback to the AI industry and policymakers (Buhmann & Fieseler 2021; 2023). However, deliberative democracy and mini-publics also face practical and theoretical obstacles, such as the complexity and opacity of AI systems, the power asymmetries and knowledge gaps

between experts and citizens, and the potential manipulation and co-optation of the deliberative processes by vested interests.

To align with the EU's digital and green transition agenda, one of the potential governance responses is to promote sustainable AI that can foster smaller and more transparent models that respect democratic values. This could be achieved by drawing lessons from the regulation of life sciences and medical industry, such as involving diverse stakeholders in the decision-making process. Moreover, more participatory approaches to AI governance and standard setting are needed overall, like support for NGOs and CSOs to engage in AI policy. This could be helped by increasing funding, institutional support, and research initiatives dedicated to fostering responsible AI practices.

4 Advancement of the State of the Art

Later versions of this module will build upon the conceptualisation of the problems posed by the use of personal data and user profiling to develop a social risk toolkit to advance the state of the art. This toolkit will take each of the identified problems in turn and provide guidance to understand, mitigate against, and account for, the ethical and legal issues in the use of personal data and user profiling.

5 Conclusion

This version of Module D of the social toolkit has conceptualised some of the risks that the use of personal data and user profiling pose to democracy. This work provides the basis for consequent versions of the social risk toolkit which will provide actionable guidance for policy and CSOs and seek to improve awareness in academia and industry.

Module E: Control of Individual Freedoms of Speech and Action

Executive Summary

This document is the result of work undertaken in task 4.1 of the KT4D project, and is the first iteration of one of the five modules (module E) of the social risk toolkit. The aim of this task was to conceptualise the current state of the art in regard to the impact of AI and big data on democracy from the perspective of governments, companies, and organisations. Later versions of this document will incorporate work from task 4.3 to advance the state of the art.

This module aims to understand how AI and big data threaten individual freedoms of speech and action. As one of the KERs of KT4D, this module contributes to the protection of human rights and democratic values. The conceptualisation of the problems posed to individual freedoms of speech and action will provide the basis for the development of a social risk toolkit later in the project. Future versions of this social risk toolkit module will also provide actionable guidance for WPs 5, 6, and 7.

The current version of this module outlines the threats that AI and big data pose to individual freedom of citizens. In **Section 1** we outline the conception of freedom this module rests upon, and how it relates to the protection of human rights and democracy. **Section 2** provides the conceptual work of this module and outlines various risks to individual freedoms including but not limited to freedom of choice, job displacement, the threat of extensive punishment, and privacy and surveillance concerns. **Section 3** provides an analysis of AI, big data and frontier technologies impact from a data protection and general human rights perspective. This includes a legal and regulatory analysis of current and proposed legislation for issues such as profiling, targeting advertising, facial recognition, and political advertising. Finally, in **Section 4** future work in task 4.3 to advance the state of the art will be briefly discussed.

1 Introduction

1.1 Overview

This version of Module E focuses on understanding risks to individual freedom of speech and action. Through a review of the current literature on AI, big data and freedom and the use of applied philosophical analysis, this module outlines some of the threats AI and big data pose to individual freedoms of speech and action. Given the focus on freedom of individuals, this module also surveys some existing legislation and regulatory frameworks for the use of AI and its impacts on citizens.

1.1.1 Structure

This module has 4 sections. Section 1 provides an outline of the conceptualisation of freedom and its relationship to democracy that this toolkit rests upon. Section 2 provides the basis for this version of the module and outlines ways that AI and big data pose a risk to individual freedoms including freedom of choice, job displacement, dehumanisation, problems of surveillance and for civil disobedience, and freedom to access information. Section 3 analyses current and emerging regulation for AI and big data. Finally, section 4 provides a brief overview of further developments for this module.

1.1.2 Scope and Limitations

This is the first version of module E of deliverable 4.1. Deliverable 4.1 is being developed out of work within WP4 that advances ethical and legal considerations in the control of freedoms of individual speech and action. Much like the other modules included in this toolkit then, this version is intended to provide a conceptual overview of some of the currently identified issues. Section 4, that will provide actionable guidance, will be developed in task 4.3. Again, like the module D, the concepts and analysis included in this module will form the basis of state of the art for WPs 5, 6 and 7.

1.2 What is Freedom?

When we think of freedom or ‘liberty’ we typically think of it in certain ways: e.g., freedom to act as we please, freedom from harm or interference, freedom of thought, or freedom to be a member of a community (Susskind, 2018: 165). Philosophers have often said that freedom insofar as it is afforded to you by others is not freedom (Dworkin, 1989: Ch 1; Pettit, 2017; Skinner, 2012). Whilst AI and big data could in several ways enhance freedom, it may also limit it.

As outlined in section 1.3 in module D, freedom and autonomy of citizens are an important aspect of democracy. Without the ability to make decisions and form opinions, citizens cannot participate in democratic deliberation. What is sometimes called republican freedom is the notion that freedom is being able to self-govern, and that if one's freedom is dependent on the benevolence of another, then this is not

truly freedom. In this respect, since online platforms can dictate what is seen and said, we are dependent on these platforms, and the algorithms that govern them, to speak freely.

Freedom in the AI and big data age may therefore look very different to our traditional conceptions of freedom, but is it still freedom nonetheless? At the very least, it seems that the use of AI and big data in society must satisfy a ‘knowledge condition’ to provide sufficient freedom for citizens (Sloan and Warner, 2019: 4). Sloan and Warner (2019: 4) suggest that this knowledge condition must be something along the lines of: “those subject to decisions of another are able with reasonable effort to know that there is an adequate justification for the decisions”. This suggests that the previous discussions about black-box thinking, transparency, and accountability in Module D are of great importance to the way we think about freedom of speech and action in the AI and big data age. In what follows, we outline some of the ways that AI and big data, and particularly ADM, threaten the freedom of citizens.

2 State of the Art

Since our liberal democracies generally employ forms of representativeness to their institutions, the impact of AI on free and fair elections is also one of the key ways in which technology affects our polities. The level of acceptance of the results from the elections - the legitimacy of the outcome - rests largely on how those who end up with less power shares in the representative system see the fairness of the election process itself. This includes the ability of individuals and groups to express their views freely, having access to information, and forming an informed opinion of the capabilities and views of candidates and parties. The EU Commission launched a study to map the issue in a recent report (Trasys International, 2021), and academic literature also indicates different ways AI can be used to influence free and fair elections. The key dimensions include: job displacement and economic inequality, privacy and surveillance, disinformation, and voter manipulation and suppression.

2.1 Job Displacement and Economic Inequality

The rapid advancement of AI and its applications in various domains has raised concerns about the impact of automation on the future of work. One of the main issues is the potential displacement of human workers by AI systems, especially in white collar jobs that require cognitive and analytical skills. These jobs were previously thought to be immune to automation, but recent studies have indicated that many of them are susceptible to being replaced or augmented by AI (Eloundou et al. 2023). This has been seen perhaps most acutely with the negative effects of generative AI on artists and writers. These effects could lead to significant changes in the labour market, such as job losses, skill mismatches, wage polarisation, and income inequality. Others emphasise the potential for new job creation and the need for skill adaptation in response to technological advancements (Autor 2015; Brynjolfsson & McAfee 2014). It is also worth noting AI can impact workers within the workplace through algorithmic management, surveillance and incentivization of productivity in order to shift risks from firms to workers (Moradi & Levy 2020). The widening scope of such labour market effects intensifies the spectre of economic inequality, contributing to socio-economic disparities and unrest that directly impinges upon democratic stability.

2.2 The Effects of AI and the Law

Because of the varying ways that AI and big data can be utilised to make predictions, its use in courts, criminal proceedings and law enforcement. This section explores some of the risks AI and big data can pose to the lives of citizens in aspects such as micro-criminality, civil disobedience, and predicting criminality.

2.2.1 Extensive Punishment and Micro-Criminality

Almost $\frac{3}{4}$ of individuals in Britain admit to having committed some minor crime (Dean, 2016). With the rise of surveillance technology, tracking us and collecting information about our activities, we might seriously constrain our freedom (Manheim and Kaplan, 2019: 126; Susskind, 2018: 172). If for example one wishes to chance not getting a TV licence, it may be significantly harder to do so when your TV can notify the authorities immediately. In other examples surveillance itself is not required, we can imagine an algorithm within a self-driving vehicle that simply doesn't allow you to exceed speed limits. Whilst this on the face of it seems to be a positive, after all, we want people to adhere to the law, we lose the ability to break it even to a minor degree (thus constraining one's autonomy). This is of particular importance in democracies when we think about the notion of civil disobedience.

2.2.2 Civil Disobedience

Civil disobedience is an act of resistance in the name of a cause of social justice. Previous examples of movements like these include women's suffrage, LGBT protests (such as Stonewall) and the black civil rights movement. Freedom to do these acts in democracy is often defended by political theorists. Rawls (2004) for example believed that even in politically liberal democratic societies, it is still possible that unjust laws can be created. We therefore ought to uphold a right to civil disobedience for the purposes of bringing about a more just society. Importantly, this must be done in a non-violent manner, with a good chance of success. The participants must also do so publicly and non-evasively (Rawls, 2004: 367).

It is not hard to see how AI and big data could improve our ability to perform acts of civil disobedience, or at least given further means by which it can be done. The advent of 'hactivist groups' such as Anonymous, who can attack government systems or infiltrate data banks, in the name of a cause may provide some evidence for this (Himma, 2007: 73; Wyant, 2012). Rawls (2004) may object to the anonymity of these groups, since in being evasive they could be perceived as calling into question the legitimacy of the institutions themselves: one ought to accept the consequences of one's actions to display what is sometimes called 'fidelity to law', to show one's acts are calls for change rather than revolution. Though it is not immediately apparent why 'fidelity to law' is the only method by which one can communicate that an act of civil disobedience is non-revolutionary. This is especially poignant when we consider our modern context, wherein all one has to do to get a message out into the world is tweet.¹⁰ Perhaps something like 'it was me! Let's change this unjust

¹⁰ Objections may be raised that algorithmic bias may mean your message is not heard. This is explored more fully in section 2.5.3.

system (but don't overthrow the government)'. Seemingly if the non-revolutionary message can be carried out regardless, we have no need for the non-evasion condition.

Although, we should also consider potential responses to this change in activism. For example, social media platforms now use encryption (encoding messages) to make hacking difficult. A consequence of this is also that it makes government surveillance on privately owned platforms more difficult (Clark, 2017; Corera, 2017). This sort of surveillance is not alien to democracies, as was exposed in the case of Edward Snowden, who leaked information that the NSA had been illegally spying on private citizens (Casciani, 2018). The increased security of private platforms has given states cause to make their own online platforms that can be surveyed more easily. WeChat in China is perhaps the best example of this, though other countries such as Turkey have also made new platforms such as their own national emailing system (Susskind, 2018: 183).

Governments can also use algorithms themselves to monitor their citizens, such as China's social credit system (Qiang, 2019: 59 – 61). As a result of this, the presence of AI and big data may make acts of civil disobedience significantly harder to organise and carry out. Especially if a government makes their own national messaging systems like that in China (WeChat (Sonnad, 2017)). Supposing for example that one wishes to organise a protest, perhaps glueing oneself to the M4 motorway. You're in groups on Facebook with other like minded individuals, all of whom have phones with location tracking software. A message is sent out to the group specifying that the protest is today, but the government targets specific words, preventing any message containing these words from being received. Perhaps somehow you find out anyway, and continue to the location, you recognise your phone could be used to track you, so you discard it. As you walk along the street, you're continually noticed by surveillance cameras, who recognise your face as being within a group known for protests of this sort. Several other individuals from your group are also spotted heading towards a similar point from several directions. Feeding this information to an AI algorithm, it calculates there is a high possibility that you and your colleagues are attempting a protest. It therefore triangulates the location to which you are all headed, and authorities are on the scene before you even arrive (Susskind, 2018). This is a scary thought. It is scary because often those changes most integral to the flourishing of liberal democratic systems are those changes brought about by acts of civil disobedience. The prospect of this freedom being curtailed or highly limited in a world of AI and big data is thus highly alarming, if we suppose that any of our current laws and social structures are unjust in a similar manner to the issues highlighted by social justice movements prior. Since it would be incredibly contentious at best to suppose society as it stands has nothing more to learn, the introduction of these systems not only risks a curtailment of freedom, but the real possibility of tyranny.

2.2.3 Predicting Criminality

A potential limit to freedom is the use of AI in determining our activity, which in turn could affect how others treat us within society. For example, there are now machine learning algorithms that have been able to predict criminality simply by looking at someone's face, with 90% accuracy (Arcas et al, 2017; Wu et al, 2016: 3). Others can use sociological, or socioeconomic factors to predict areas of criminality, for the allocation of law enforcement resources (Castelli et al, 2017). If these factors can be used as predictors of activity, then a few things result: (1) our activity is far less determined by us than we originally thought (Susskind: 2018: 176),

and/or (2) the state having access to this information can further exacerbate structural issues within law enforcement.

2.3 Voter Manipulation and Suppression

AI can largely influence the self-rule of the *demos* through shaping the information environments in different ways (Jungherr 2023). As a distinct dimension affecting free and fair elections, AI can be used to target and manipulate voters. By analysing vast amounts of data, AI systems can identify specific demographics and target them with tailored messages to shape their views and behaviour. This micro-targeting can potentially lead to manipulation, undermining the integrity of electoral processes (Jungherr 2023). Different ways of manipulation are still at the projection phase, which means some of the concrete impacts still remain to be seen and depend also on the level of technology in question. Noorman and Swierstra (2023) make a distinction between how AI can affect recognizing, resisting, deliberating, voting, representing, joining, and exiting within democracies.

2.4 Privacy and Surveillance

AI systems can collect and analyse large amounts of personal information from various sources, such as social media, online platforms, and biometric devices. This data can be used to profile, target, manipulate, or influence voters, as well as to monitor and suppress dissent (Coeckelbergh 2022b). Unauthorised access to personal data by hackers, foreign actors, or malicious insiders can compromise the security and integrity of elections, as well as expose sensitive information about individuals' preferences, opinions, and behaviours. Moreover, the use of surveillance technologies, such as facial recognition, drones, and smart cameras, can erode privacy and civil liberties, creating a chilling effect on democratic participation and free expression. As AI becomes more ubiquitous and powerful, the protection of privacy and surveillance becomes a crucial issue for ensuring the legitimacy and fairness of elections (Privacy International 2019).

In a world of increasing surveillance, whoever controls the technology (and the access to the data it provides) will have an enormous amount of power (Susskind, 2018: 124). In one respect this could create better people, since individuals behave differently when they know they're being observed, on the other hand this could put vast amounts of power in the hands of the government and would make the goals of a tyrannical government very easy.

2.5 Access and Evaluation of Information

AI algorithms on digital media platforms owned by private companies are now in a new and powerful position. They govern what type of deliberation is permissible, who it is seen by, and when. In effect this means AI algorithms owned by private companies are continuously regulating our ability to deliberate. This results in several issues for the value of freedom in democracy with respect to deliberation, but also several advantages.

First, the internet provides us with a great deal of information and may be a large forum by which deliberation can be done on a wide scale.¹¹ These platforms can be used to enhance deliberation, not merely in the public sphere, but with potential for implementation through online digital assemblies. However, in no way does this mean the deliberation is of good quality. Resulting from total anonymity, ‘online trolls’ – lacking face-to-face interaction and individual accountability – make good faith deliberation ever more difficult (Bartlett, 2018: Ch 1; Manheim and Kaplan, 2019: 127 – 128). AI-assisted algorithms, with their focus on engagement, can also make deliberation difficult.

Moreover, since these platforms offer lower accountability (because discussion can be anonymous) a greater diversity of discussions can occur without the issues of social taboo. Additionally, these platforms, in theory, give louder voices to minority groups and allow them to congregate in online spaces; finding each other and presenting their opinions to the wider public as a collective. Many social justice movements now heavily rely on online platforms and utilise the algorithms that spread information to present new points of discussion. These risks of AI to our epistemic freedoms are discussed below under the themes of epistemically assisting freedom (2.5.1), risks to the quality of information (2.5.2) and risks to the quality of discourse (2.5.3).

2.5.1 Epistemically Assisting Freedom

Often a criticism of democratic decision making is that individuals within democracy are not good judges for making democratic decisions. However, some have proposed that increased human augmentation with AI systems would solve this epistemic problem (Fuller, 2018: 3). Already we see this in a minor sense when looking at ‘fact checkers’ on platforms such as X (formerly Twitter). But some have speculated that this may increase in the coming years. Devices such as ‘neuralink’ could provide augmented humans with access to online information which could greatly enhance our ability to make reliably well-informed decisions (Gurtner, 2021). Following a similar vein to the fact checking system on X, such a system might be able to provide live fact checking in one’s daily life and give one access to a wealth of information previously unavailable. However, relying on such a technology would pose serious issues, and it has been argued that the development and mechanisms of this technology should be sufficiently transparent to the public (Fourneret, 2020: 671).

We might also be able to enhance our intellectual abilities through technology, giving us access to large amounts of data, making us more informed and therefore ‘freer’ as our actions would be more likely to adhere to our desires, and our desires more likely to adhere to our interests (Susskind, 2018: 167). However, what could be perceived as an enhancement on freedom, could equally be seen as a form of manipulation when we consider where the information comes from, and who has presented it (Susskind, 2018: 167). Suggestions of maintaining ‘cerebral hygiene’ to prevent bias and manipulation seem counterintuitive in the context of public political deliberation as we may become incredibly uninformed on many important issues (Griffiths, 1997: 130; Haac, 2018).

Some have also suggested that the influence of others only becomes manipulative when it offers no opportunity for an individual to reflect on or discuss the information (Susskind, 2018: 171; Sunstein, 2016).

¹¹ This is explored further in module D.

If such information does not generate answers, but provides information for you to consider, then the issue of manipulation may be circumvented.

2.5.2 Quality of Information

The intersection of AI and disinformation campaigns in electoral processes has been a focal point in scholarly discourse. Study by Allcott and Gentzkow (2017) shed light on how social media and AI are harnessed to orchestrate and propagate sophisticated disinformation. Advanced algorithms wielded in generating fabricated news articles, deep fake videos, and manipulated images contribute to a disconcerting landscape where discerning truth from falsehood becomes increasingly challenging for users. This manipulation, as underscored by Lazer et al. (2018), not only undermines trust in democratic institutions but also disrupts the foundational principles of informed decision-making within electoral contexts. The proliferation of AI-driven disinformation campaigns underscores the imperative for multifaceted strategies, including technological solutions and media literacy initiatives, to counteract the deleterious effects on democratic processes and restore the integrity of information dissemination in electoral arenas. Aside from fake news, AI can also more deceptively affect self-rule by shaping information environments, economics of news, speech and manipulation on a structural level, as noted by Jungherr (2023).

Typically, in politics prior, what was disputed when we were making decisions was ‘what we ought to do in lieu of the facts’. Now with AI algorithms feeding alternative accounts of the facts to each respective echo chamber, what is now being deliberated is what ‘the facts’ even are (Susskind: 2018: 230). This is harmful for democratic deliberation since deliberation is intended to accommodate reasonable moral disagreement (Gutmann and Thompson, 2004: Ch 1). If person A and B disagree about what the facts of the case are, then any claim of what we ought to do from either party cannot be used until this first disagreement is resolved. Whilst this disagreement about facts may have existed prior to AI-generated content, the sheer volume of alternative facts, and the way they are pushed towards specific user types, presents a further challenge.

Moreover, the participation of AI bots in online discourse can undermine the quality of information. These are AI algorithms that pretend to be people in online spaces. Often this is harmful to deliberation since they spread false information or pretend to forward an extreme ideological position to further exacerbate division (Susskind, 2018: 232). Bots have also been found to target other bots activities in online spaces: thus, in a way deliberation itself is now being automated (Sample, 2017; Tsvetkova et al, 2016).

2.5.3 Diversity of Discourse

Since in the digital world we now live in, public discourse is conducted in online spaces, and these spaces are governed by private companies, this makes digital media companies responsible for several things. First, they can decide what is worth reporting, and what isn’t, thus they can potentially limit the impact of information harmful to their own interest but in the interest of the public (Susskind, 2018: 143). However, the internet also provides a large marketplace from which smaller sources of information can have an impact (Benkler, 2006: 177 – 178). Previously the news was reserved for the mainstream media.

They can also limit what topics can be discussed on their platforms by their users. If left in the hands of private firms then, a severe issue may result in that some political opinions are deliberately withheld, and others are emphasised (Susskind, 2018). In a less overt manner, this could be done by only presenting one particular position in a negative way. This subversion through digital media has been termed by Zittrain et al as ‘digital gerrymandering’ (Zittrain et. al, 2014).

Filtering is also done through search engines: as any given search creates millions of results, the information must be rank ordered (Granka, 2010: 266). As such, the information given to us through these systems – by the method of the systems – determines what we get to know. Even though we have access to other search results, we cannot see them all, nor can we be sure why the first search results were shown. This is a powerful tool to take advantage of. Stewart, Cichocki and McLeod (2022) outline the ways that social media algorithms “sort and target” information, typically based on likelihood of engagement.¹² Moreover, search engine algorithms have been found to ‘push’ a fairly limited range of new sources (Nechushtai and Lewis, 2019).

Firms also have their own financial interests, as such it is not always in their interest to give an equal platform to all users (Susskind, 2018: 193). In this respect, we have two diametrically opposed rights that seem hard to reconcile. If we view platforms as a public good, or in some way linked to the deliberative process of democracy, it stands to reason that each person should have equal access to it as a resource regardless of their views. However, these platforms are privately owned, and therefore they also seemingly reserve the right to refuse service and exclude people from using it.

Whilst firms themselves cannot be held to account in the same way as governments, there are conceivable methods for regulating what they can and cannot do, and why they can or cannot do it.¹³ However, the AI algorithms that are used in these platforms are self-learning (Susskind, 2018: 193). They are given an initial goal, but the methods by which this goal is achieved is often unknown to even the creators of the algorithms (Arbesman, 2017; Pasquale, 2015). This means algorithms may incidentally use discriminatory processes to better achieve their desired outcome (Favaretto, 2019: 12; Tanna et al, 2022: 441). These discriminatory processes may reinforce and exacerbate existing injustices in society. For example, Stewart, Cichocki and McLeod (2022) detail how the algorithmic decisions made on social media can reify the conditions for epistemic injustice by not supporting diversity in discourse.

3 Legal and Regulatory Frameworks

The purpose of this section of the deliverable is to provide an overview of how AI, big data and frontier technologies impact rights from the data protection perspective. The newly adopted definition of AI by the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) states that “an AI system is a machine-based system that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that (can) influence physical or virtual

¹² For more on algorithmic targeting and sorting see section 2.2.1 in module D.

¹³ For detail on existing and emerging regulation of AI and big data see section 3 in module D.

environments. Different AI systems vary in their levels of autonomy and adaptiveness after deployment ” (OECD.AI, 2023).

On the one hand, big data is defined as “high-volume, high-velocity and high-variety information assets that demand cost-effective, innovative forms of information processing for enhanced insight and decision making” (Definition of big data - Gartner Information Technology Glossary). On the other hand, the OECD defines frontier technologies as those which will “reshape industry and communications and provide urgently needed solutions to global challenges like climate change and have the potential to displace existing processes”. Frontier technologies include knowledge technologies such as blockchain, AI, IoT and VR (OECD Science, Technology and Industry Scoreboard, 2017). This section of the deliverable will focus on frontier technologies, as the current regulatory frameworks often do, however these frontier technologies include knowledge technologies.

The section will provide a legal and regulatory analysis of currently applicable and proposed legislation concerning frontier technologies as well as the legal framework applicable to profiling and targeted advertising, and in particular, facial recognition, political advertising. It will also provide an analysis of the risks for data transfers to negatively impact democracy and fundamental rights and highlight the risks or challenges and opportunities in terms of rights and democracy with respect to frontier technologies with specific reference to their application in both the public and private sectors.

This deliverable aims to provide an overview of some of the problems which AI and big data pose to democracy from a perspective of government, organisations and companies. The use of frontier technologies by both private and public sector actors has increased and the use is being influenced by the application of big data (ICO, 2013a). The use of such technologies thus has an impact on privacy, data protection and other individual’s rights that are strengthened by different legal and regulatory frameworks (ICO, 2013b).

3.1 Applicable Legal and Regulatory Framework

This subsection concerns the legal and regulatory analysis of currently applicable as well as proposed legislation concerning frontier technologies in addition to the legal framework applicable to profiling and targeted advertising and in particular, facial recognition, political advertising.

The legal framework that will be discussed includes the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the ePrivacy Directive, the European Convention on Human Rights (ECHR), the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union (the Charter), the draft AI Act, the Digital Services Act package, and 2021/0381 (COD) Transparency and targeting of political advertising.

There are also significant sector-specific regulations on AI for which we have prepared a review that has mapped the various instruments. While the following sections provide information on applicable and proposed legislation concerning frontier technologies, a broader set of guidelines on relevant legal and ethical frameworks applicable to AI are provided in Appendix I. For the purpose of this T4.1, we have selected the following guidelines which we will discuss due to their relevance: EU AI Strategy, the EU Commission’s

White Paper on AI, the proposed AI Act and High-level Expert Group (HLEG) Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy and Ethical AI.

Each piece of actual and forthcoming legislation will be analysed to the extent they regulate applications of AI & big data (and specifically, profiling, targeted and political advertising, and facial recognition) with the aim of upholding fundamental rights and democracy.

3.1.1 EU Legal Data Protections Framework: The General Data Protection Regulation and the ePrivacy Directive

The GDPR is the world's most comprehensive and progressive data protection law. Privacy and data protection as rights are enshrined in the EU Treaties and in the Charter. Article 8 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights (ECHR) protects the right to respect for private life, the home and correspondence. This includes protecting the privacy of messages, phone calls, and emails.

The scope of application of the GDPR is in relation to data processing activities that take place using the information which relates to an identified or identifiable individual called a data subject located within the EU. Article 4(1) of the GDPR defines an identifiable individual as one who can be identified either directly or indirectly by reference to an identifier e.g., name, location data, an online identifier etc.

The GDPR covers two types of personal data, i.e., common personal data such as name, surname, location data, financial information, etc. and also, special categories of personal data under Article 9 of the GDPR. Special categories of data require a higher level of protection. They include genetic data, health data, biometric data, information about race or ethnic origin, political opinions, religious or philosophical beliefs, trade union membership and information on sex life or sexual orientation.

The ePrivacy Directive is a legal instrument that sets the standard for all entities which store or access information stored in the terminal equipment of a subscriber or user in the EEA. A terminal equipment under the ePrivacy Directive is defined as that which is directly or indirectly connected to the interface of a public telecommunications network to send, process or receive information, or a satellite earth equipment.

In general, the ePrivacy Directive and the GDPR help ensure digital privacy for residents of the EU. The ePrivacy Directive requires EU countries to ensure that users grant their consent before cookies are stored and accessed in computers, smartphones or another device connected to the Internet. A cookie is a small file, typically of letters and numbers, downloaded onto a device when the user accesses certain websites (ICO, 2012).

The GDPR and ePrivacy Directive regulate profiling and targeted advertising (in particular, facial recognition, political advertising) by providing for certain conditions to be met such as ensuring users' informed consent. Consent of data subjects is the legal basis for advertising. Article 4(11) of the GDPR requires consent to be a freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous indication of data subjects' wishes, given through a statement or a clear affirmative action. Similarly, the ePrivacy Directive requires users' consent for cookies and other tracking devices that interfere with the users' terminal equipment.

3.1.1.1 The General Data Protection Regulation

Article 85 of the GDPR recognizes the need for the protection of freedom of expression and grants EU Member States the power to adopt, where necessary, statutory derogations to a large part of the GDPR itself, including data processing principles, data subject's rights and rules on international transfers. In the EU, privacy and data protection are commonly recognised as important components for a sustainable democracy (Data Protection, EDPS).

Although privacy is among the rights enshrined in the ECHR, the GDPR has shaped up the protection of democracy due to the fact that entities have an obligation to demonstrate what personal data they are processing. In order to retain trust and confidence of the public and the integrity of the elections, organisations involved in political campaigning and political aspirants must use personal data and campaigning techniques in ways that are transparent and informed (Democracy disrupted? Personal information and political influence-ICO, 2018). The transparency principle and the right to information of the data subjects are requirements for processing of personal data under the GDPR (see Arts. 5(1)(a), 12, 13, and 14 GDPR).

Political opinions are among the special categories of personal data that are accorded protection under Article 9 of the GDPR. As a general rule, processing such data listed above is **prohibited**. However, under certain limitations, an entity may be allowed to process sensitive personal data. They include:

- Where sensitive data has been manifestly made public;
- Where the data subject has given their explicit consent;
- Where there is a law which governs a specific type of data processing for a specific purpose related to public interest or health;
- Where a law including adequate safeguards provides for the processing of sensitive personal data in areas such as public health, employment and social protection.

In general, effective data protection and meaningful privacy rights support democratic processes, participation and debate (Joint Statement on Privacy and Democratic Rights- OPCC, 2023).

3.1.1.1.1 The Importance of Data Protection in AI

In recent years, AI has gone through rapid development and has provided opportunities for economic, social, and cultural development. The opportunities are accompanied by serious risks e.g., unemployment, inequality, discrimination, social exclusion, surveillance, and manipulation (The impact of the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) on artificial intelligence - EPRS, 2020a). This necessitates the need for effective regulation of AI. Several AI systems process personal data. The personal data may be used as data sets to train the machine learning systems i.e., to build algorithmic models. Personal data may also be to infer certain habits concerning individuals.

The GDPR does not explicitly mention AI. However, several GDPR provisions are directly applicable to the deployment of AI systems. The GDPR principles and rights can be interpreted in a manner that is compatible with AI and big data. For example, the right to information of data subjects under Article 13 GDPR should enable data subjects to understand the purpose of each AI-based processing and its limits (EPRS, 2020b).

Similarly, the principles of data protection by design and by default under Article 25 GDPR should be taken into consideration in the development of AI and will not hinder their development in the case where the AI systems are correctly designed and implemented (EPRS, 2020c).

The obligation to carry out a DPIA under Article 35 GDPR where the processing of personal data is likely to result in a high risk is likely required when looking into the deployment of AI systems to process personal data.¹⁴

The State Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information in Baden-Württemberg in its Discussion paper on when and how personal data may be processed for the training and application of AI noted that the processing of large sets of personal data in AI systems bears the risk that the data will become special categories of personal data over the course of the processing lifecycle (LfDI BW, 2023). The requirements for processing of special categories of personal data under Article 9 GDPR should thus be taken into consideration. Generally, the citizens' trust in the ability to innovate and use AI systems in a responsible manner requires that data protection requirements are implemented.

3.1.1.1.1 Data Protection Principles and Other Relevant Aspects of Data Protection Law

The GDPR outlines key principles which influence other rules and obligations set out in the legislation. Compliance with the fundamental principles of data protection is a step towards ensuring the fulfilment of obligations under the GDPR. The data protection principles set out in Article 5 of the GDPR help redress the imbalance between the individuals and the entities that process personal data.

Compliance with the data protection principles and data protection law in general, preserves democracy while also protecting the individual in the face of development of frontier technologies and generates trust in the digital economy (Data Protection Principles-Jersey Office of the Information Commissioner, 2019). The data protection principles will be explained in relation to enhancing democracy in the subsequent sections. However a more detailed description of the data processing principles is set out in the Data Management Plan, D1.1.

¹⁴ As stated in D8.3, note that “Article 35 GDPR requires that DPIAs are carried out in certain cases; specifically where a data processing activity and specifically a new technology, is ‘likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons’. DPIAs therefore do not need to be carried out for all data processing activities. That being said, DPIAs represent a useful accountability tool which can be relied upon by data controllers to ensure data protection compliance.” Activities which may be considered to be highly risky include profiling, the “processing on a large scale of special categories of data referred to in Article 9(1), or of personal data relating to criminal convictions and offences referred to in Article 10”, the “Innovative use or applying technological or organisational solutions” and “data processed on a large scale”. See Article 29 Working Party Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is “likely to result in a high risk” for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679, 4 April 2017.

3.1.1.1.1.2 *Lawfulness, Fairness and Transparency*

Article 5(1)(a) of the GDPR requires that personal data is processed lawfully, fairly and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject. The processing of personal data for various operations must include a legal basis pursuant to Article 6 of the GDPR. At least one valid lawful basis must exist for the lawful processing of personal data which must be determined prior to the processing of personal data. Legal bases under Article 6 GDPR include consent, contractual necessity, for compliance with a legal obligation, to protect the vital interests of a data subject or other person, for the performance of a task in the public interests, and for the purpose of legitimate interest.

Transparency in processing operations entails being clear, open and honest with data subjects about the identity of the data controller, what they intend to do with the personal data and why they need to process the specific personal data. All this should be made clear prior to the processing operations (ICO, n.p.)

Fairness implies that the processing of personal data shall be done in a way in which the data subjects may reasonably expect their data to be processed and may not be used in an unlawful manner. Fairness also entails that data is not used in a manner that would have unjustified effects on data subjects (ICO, n.p.).

In enhancing democracy, fairness relates to developing a regulatory framework where the rights of the citizens with respect to their personal data are respected and the existing inequality in bargaining power between them and governments and companies that process their personal data are mitigated. In such a framework, the individual must have control over their personal data since they are the data principal in the digital economy (Committee of Experts under the Chairmanship of Justice B.N. Srikrishna, 2018: 14a). The relationship between the individual and entities with whom the individual shares their personal data is based on a fundamental expectation of trust (Committee of Experts under the Chairmanship of Justice B.N. Srikrishna, 2018: 14b). The individual thus expects that their personal data will be used fairly, in a manner that fulfils their interest and is reasonably foreseeable.

Some of the principles for reforms to enhance accountability of frontier technologies, including providing robust protection for citizens' privacy include increasing transparency about platform's algorithms (The White House, 2023). These principles are important in ensuring that individuals are involved in decision making concerning their personal data and to ensure that states and entities that gather and record citizens personal data are transparent about the data they have followed fair and lawful processes in the collection, use, retention and maintenance of security of that data (Article 19, 2017).

3.1.1.1.1.3 *Purpose Limitation, Data Minimisation, Storage Limitation*

The purpose limitation principle under Article 5(1)(b) of the GDPR requires personal data to be collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not further processed in a manner that is incompatible with the original purposes. Instead, the principle of data minimisation established under Article 5(1)(c) of the GDPR requires the data controller to limit personal data to what is directly relevant and necessary in order to achieve a specific purpose for which the data are processed (ICO, n.p.).

The storage limitation principle under Article 5(1)(e) GDPR requires that personal data is only kept in a form that allows for the identification of data subjects for as long as is necessary for the purposes of processing of personal data. These principles specifically aim to reduce risks to the rights and freedoms of individuals (ICO, n.p.).

3.1.1.1.1.4 Necessity and Proportionality

Necessity is an important principle in assessing the restriction of fundamental rights e.g., the right to the protection of personal data. It is also important when assessing the lawfulness of the processing of personal data. The processing of personal data shall only be carried out when necessary and the duration in which the data is stored shall be necessary for the purpose of processing (EDPS, 2020a).

The principle of proportionality is a general principle enshrined in EU law which restricts governments, companies and organisations in the exercise of their powers by requiring them to strike a balance between the means used and the aim they intend to achieve (EDPS, 2020b).

Proportionality is fundamental for the limitation of fundamental rights such as the right to the protection of personal data (EDPS, 2020c). Proportionality requires that only personal data that is adequate and relevant for the purposes of processing is collected and processed.

3.1.1.1.1.5 Accuracy

Article 5(1)(d) of the GDPR outlines the principle of accuracy which requires that personal data is accurate and kept up to date. This places an obligation on entities to rectify or erase inaccurate data without delay. Where the accuracy of personal data is contested by the data subject, Article 18(1) of the GDPR gives a data subject the right to obtain a restriction of processing of their personal data. In order to enhance access to information for citizens, governments must establish an accurate record keeping system.

3.1.1.1.1.6 Integrity and Confidentiality – Data Security

Article 5(1)(f) of the GDPR necessitates that personal data is processed in a manner that ensures appropriate security of personal data. The principle also requires protection against unauthorised or unlawful processing and against accidental loss, destruction or damage. The data security principle has been reaffirmed in Article 32 GDPR. This article necessitates that appropriate technical and organisational measures are implemented to ensure a level of security which is appropriate to the risk which arises as a result of the data processing activity. Data security measures and online restrictions that are implemented by governments, organisations or companies must align with international human rights law and standards and this includes the protection against among other things, unethical hacking, data interception and identity theft (Open Internet for Democracy, 2023).

3.1.1.1.1.7 Accountability

The accountability principle under Article 5(2) of the GDPR places a requirement on data controllers to be able to demonstrate compliance with other data protection principles. The Article 29 Working Party Guidelines on transparency under Regulation 2016/679 re-affirm that data controllers must also comply with

the accountability principle under the GDPR which should be applied throughout the life cycle of data processing.

The principle of accountability is an important piece of good governance that enables the citizens to gain control over the use of public resources. It contributes to limiting the risk of abuse of power and corrupt practices, which in turn guarantees the fulfilment of citizens' rights. Where governments, organisations and companies have a well-functioning accountability mechanism, it enhances trust in the management of citizens affairs. The accountability principle thus places an obligation on the relevant actors including governments, to inform the public and justify their decisions. This places an information obligation on the actors and is related to the rights of the citizens to get information and get an explanation relating to the actions of governments, organisations and companies.

3.1.1.1.1.8 Data Protection by Design and by Default

Article 25 of the GDPR lays down the principle of data protection by design. The principle requires the data controller, at the time of determination of the means for processing and during the processing itself, to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures which are designed to implement data protection principles in an effective manner in order to meet the requirements of the GDPR. The principle also requires the controller to implement appropriate technical and organisational measures to ensure that, by default, only personal data which is necessary for a specific purpose is processed.

When governments, organisations and companies enable the principle of data protection by design and by default in the building of systems, they will build foundations of trustworthy data sharing (Sophie Stalla-Bourdillon, et al., 2020a). Governments, organisations and companies should build a workflow based on trust as a fundamental consideration in order to facilitate data sharing and ultimately, create benefit to individuals and society at large (Sophie Stalla-Bourdillon, et al., 2020b).

3.1.1.1.2 Data Protection Rights

Chapter III of the GDPR recognizes the rights of data subjects to include the right to be informed, the right of access to their personal data the right to rectification of inaccurate information about them, the right to erasure or the right be forgotten, the right to restriction of processing, the right to data portability, the right to object to the processing of their personal data, and the right of data subjects to not be subjected to decisions based solely on automated processing including profiling which produces legal or similar effects (see Articles 12, 15-22 GDPR).

These data protection rights are not absolute rights and certain data protection rights only apply in certain circumstances. For example, the right to erasure only applies where personal data is no longer required for the purpose it was originally collected. Recital 4 of the GDPR provides that the right to protection of personal data must be considered in relation to its function in society and balanced against other fundamental rights.

The GDPR facilitates access to justice in multiple ways and facilitates the fight against discrimination (ICT Insider, 2024). This has been demonstrated through the provisions that allow for the exercise of data

subjects' rights and have ultimately led to enforcement actions by the EU Supervisory Authorities. An example of such an enforcement action is the fine of EUR 1.9 million issued by the Bremen Data Protection Authority against a Bremen-based housing company which was found to have unlawfully processed the personal data of over 9,500 potential tenants (BREBAU GmbH, 2022). The company processed data such as skin colour, information relating to the health of the data subjects and sexual orientation and failed to respond to the requests from data subjects. This resulted in the issuance of a fine against the company.

Essentially, the exercise of the rights of data subjects facilitates the access to justice of individuals and promote healthy democratic practices such as promoting an environment that protects individuals from discrimination based on certain factors such as their political affiliations.

3.1.1.1.3 Risks and Opportunities

There are a number of risks and opportunities for individuals that may be presented and need to be carefully considered in the application of the data protection legislation. More specifically, the discussion on vulnerable groups of persons arises due to the inequality, power imbalances and social injustices (Gianclaudio, et al., 2020a). Vulnerable groups are persons who are often considered to be legally incompetent, persons who cannot give their consent, or persons that may suffer adverse consequences in the case where their data became publicly available (Ethics in Social Science and Humanities Guidelines, 2021). The Article 29 Working Party (WP29), now known as the European Data Protection Board (EDPB) affirms that the key factor in identifying individual vulnerability is the existence of a power imbalance between the data subject and the data controller (Guidelines on Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) and determining whether processing is "likely to result in a high risk, Article 29 Working Party). The WP29 lists some of the vulnerable data subjects to include children due to the fact that they are not able to knowingly consent or object to the processing of their personal data. Employees, mentally ill persons, asylum seekers, the elderly and patients are also considered to be vulnerable groups and require special protection.

In the data protection framework, vulnerable groups emerge from the possible harms to which individuals are exposed to. Data driven systems may be tools of potential discrimination which may ultimately lead to physical and psychological harms (Gianclaudio, et al., 2020b). There are several examples from law enforcement, banking, welfare, recruitment and housing that have demonstrated that technologies can contribute to social inequalities and lead to discrimination in the access to goods and services. An example of an enforcement action from the Dutch Data Protection Authority that demonstrates the effects of discrimination posed by the deployment of technologies include the EUR 2.75 million on the Dutch tax authorities (Dutch Supervisory Authority (AP), 2021a). According to the DPA, for several years the Tax and Customs Administration has processed the (dual) nationality of applicants for childcare allowance in an unlawful, discriminatory, and therefore improper manner, resulting in serious violations of the GDPR (Dutch Supervisory Authority (AP), 2021b).

In January 2014, such data should have already been deleted but in May 2018, it was found that the dual nationality of 1,4 million people was still registered in the system of the tax authorities (Dutch Supervisory Authority (AP), 2021c). The Dutch tax authorities had processed this personal data (i.e., dual nationality) for three main reasons i.e., to assess whether an application for child benefits should be granted (such data on

nationality was stored in the Benefits system (TVS), to combat organised fraud; and to determine whether certain tax-benefit applications were of a high-risk (i.e., not granting tax benefit because nationality is linked to an extremist group) (Dutch Supervisory Authority (AP), 2021d). Ultimately, if data protection rights in the use of frontier technologies are not carefully considered and implemented, it may adversely impact data subjects.

Specific attention needs to be given in the processing of personal data belonging to vulnerable groups with regards to the obligations of data controllers. For example, WP29 Opinion on legitimate interests notes that when data controllers are performing the balance test that is required in order to process personal data on the basis of legitimate interests (Article 6(1)(f) GDPR), they need to consider the status of the data controller and data subject, including the “balance of power between the data subject and the data controller, or whether the data subject is a child or otherwise belongs to a more vulnerable segment of the population” (Article 29 WP, 2014).

Ultimately, in the case cited above, the tax authorities acted in a discriminatory way. In each of the three scenarios, under which dual nationality of citizens was processed, it was found that such data is irrelevant. The Dutch DPA emphasised the fact that the improper processing of one’s nationality not only infringed the GDPR but also infringed the fundamental right to not be discriminated against (Dutch Supervisory Authority (AP), 2021e).

Data controllers must therefore specifically pay attention to their special obligations towards vulnerable groups in order to avoid data processing related risks. For instance, the principle of transparency which requires information addressed to the data subject to be concise, easily accessible and easy to understand, and plain language used should be taken into account in the processing of personal data belonging to vulnerable groups.

3.1.2 EU AI Strategy

The EU AI strategy’s objective is to make the EU a world class hub for AI and also ensure that AI is human-centric and trustworthy (Shaping Europe’s digital future, European Commission). The aim translates into the European approach to excellence and trust through concrete rules and actions. Building trustworthy AI systems will create an innovation friendly environment for users, developers and deployers and the EC has proposed three key pillars that will enhance building trustworthy AI (European Commission, 2024a).

- A legal framework for AI that will uphold fundamental rights and address safety risks specific to the AI systems. This regulatory proposal aims to provide AI developers, deployers and users with clear requirements and obligations relating to the use of AI. The EU has now reached to a political agreement concerning the draft AI Act and the text of the legislation will now have to be formally adopted by both Parliament and Council to become EU law (European Commission, 2023);
- A civil liability framework — adapting liability rules to the digital age and AI. This will ensure among other things that victims are compensated for damages caused by unsafe products, including digital products and AI systems (European Commission, n.p.); and

- The revision of sectoral safety legislation (European Commission, 2024b).

3.1.2.1 Commission’s White Paper on AI

In 2020, the European Commission (EC) released “A White paper on Artificial Intelligence — A European approach to excellence and trust” which aims at providing a definition of AI, outlines its benefits and technological advances in different areas e.g., medicine, security and farming, as well as identifying potential risks. Some of the potential risks laid out include gender inequality, discrimination and lack of privacy (European Commission, 2020a).

The White Paper recognizes that AI is grounded in values and fundamental rights such as human dignity and privacy protection and thus technologies have to be developed in compliance with the rules in order to protect citizens rights and to give them confidence in the use of their data by government, organisations and companies. The EC emphasised the importance of enhancing digital literacy for all citizens and raising awareness relating to data privacy, transparency, the definition of AI, data governance, responsibility, and trust and dual-use of technologies (European Commission, 2020b). This will have an overall positive effect in fostering democracy for the citizens.

3.1.2.2 Proposed AI Act

Article 1 of the proposed AI Act lays down the harmonised rules for the use and placing of AI in the market, and it prohibits certain types of AI systems which are considered to be particularly risky, also laying down the specific requirements for high-risk AI systems in addition to placing obligations for operators of such systems.

The regulation aims at ensuring that fundamental rights, democracy, the rule of law and environmental sustainability are shielded from high-risk AI, while at the same time boosting innovation and making the EU a leader in the field (European Parliament, 2023a).

The AI Act outlines rules which follow a risk-based approach. The draft legislation suggests that a lighter legal regime applies to AI applications with a negligible risk, and that applications with an unacceptable risk are banned. Unacceptable risks are those that pose a threat to the safety, livelihoods and rights of the people e.g., the use of toys using voice assistance encouraging dangerous behaviour of minors.

As mentioned above, at the time of writing, the EU had reached a political agreement concerning the draft AI Act and the text of the legislation will now have to be formally adopted by both Parliament and Council to become EU law (European Parliament, 2023b). This section of the deliverable will therefore be updated according to relevant progress made on the Act in the coming months.

The draft AI Act requires the design and development of AI systems in a way that achieves an appropriate level of accuracy, robustness and cybersecurity, and perform consistently in those respects throughout their lifecycle. A more detailed description of the text of the draft AI Act is set out in the D1.1 DMP.

3.1.2.3 Trustworthy and Ethical AI

As part of its initial work on AI, the European Commission established the High-level Expert Group on AI (HLEG). The Group produced a total of four deliverables:

- Deliverable 1: Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI – these Guidelines suggest taking a “human-centric approach on AI” and establish a set of seven requirements for trustworthy AI;
- Deliverable 2: Policy and Investment Recommendations for Trustworthy AI – this document contains 33 “recommendations to guide trustworthy AI towards sustainability, growth, competitiveness, and inclusion” and aim to “empower, benefit and protect European citizens”;
- Deliverable 3: The final Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI) – the ALTAI is an innovative online tool which permits developers to carry out a self-assessment against the Ethics Guidelines;
- Deliverable 4: Sectoral Considerations on the Policy and Investment Recommendations – this document provides information on ways to implement the recommendations provided in the above documents.

This subsection will provide a brief introduction into the Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI.

3.1.2.3.1 Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI

The HLEG’s Ethics Guidelines for Trustworthy AI, published on 8 April 2019 recall that trustworthy AI must first be lawful, in that it must comply with all legal requirements (HLEG, 2019: 2a). Second, AI must be ethical, meaning that it must adhere to values and ethical principles and third, it must be robust both socially and technically (HLEG, 2019: 2b).

Throughout the design, development, and deployment of AI, these factors must be considered. Specifically, adherence to ethical principles include ensuring that the AI system is fair, that human autonomy is respected, that harm is prevented, and that systems can be explained (HLEG, 2019: 2c). Furthermore, disadvantaged, or vulnerable groups should be specifically considered (HLEG, 2019: 2d). This is particularly important in situations where a power asymmetry may be present such as in the employment context (HLEG, 2019: 2e). To this end, specific risk management processes and procedures should be put in place to mitigate potential risks arising from the use of AI (HLEG, 2019: 2e).

The seven requirements for trustworthy AI outlined by the HLEG are:

1. human agency and oversight,
2. technical robustness and safety,
3. privacy and data governance,
4. transparency,

5. diversity, non-discrimination and fairness,
6. environmental and societal well-being, and
7. accountability (Ibid).

These requirements must be taken into consideration throughout the lifecycle of AI, i.e., from design and development through the deployment phases (HLEG, 2019: 2f). In order to ensure this, clear policies and procedures must be established and followed.

The limitations and capabilities of AI systems must be clear, and individuals should always be informed that they are interacting with an AI system (HLEG, 2019: 3a). Furthermore, AI systems must be auditable, and decisions made by it traceable, a requirement which takes on particular relevance in situations where rights may be impacted (HLEG, 2019: 3b). It is considered a best practice to involve different stakeholders in the development of systems, which may contribute to identifying potential harms.

Importantly, due to the fact that “there might be fundamental tensions between different principles and requirements”, it is necessary to “Continuously identify, evaluate, document and communicate these trade-offs and their solutions” (HLEG, 2019: 3c).

Assessment lists such as the ALTAI (HLEG, 2020c) may be relied upon, bearing in mind that no assessment is entirely complete and should be part of a continuous monitoring process, if possible, also involving affected stakeholders and experts with diverse types of knowledge to ensure comprehensiveness to the extent possible.

The ALTAI (HLEG, 2020b) is meant to be completed with the assistance of designers and developers of the AI system, management, legal and/or compliance officers, data scientists, procurement specialists, and front-end staff who will use/work with the system.

As a first step, it is suggested that a Fundamental Rights Impact Assessment (FRIA) is carried out (HLEG, 2020: 5). The FRIA is meant to examine the impact of the AI system on fundamental rights such as those provided in the European Convention on Human Rights. The HLEG suggests the following questions as a basis for the FRIA:

“1. Does the AI system potentially negatively discriminate against people on the basis of any of the following grounds (non-exhaustively): sex, race, colour, ethnic or social origin, genetic features, language, religion or belief, political or any other opinion, membership of a national minority, property, birth, disability, age or sexual orientation?

Have you put in place processes to test and monitor for potential negative discrimination (bias) during the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system?

Have you put in place processes to address and rectify for potential negative discrimination (bias) in the AI system?

2. Does the AI system respect the rights of the child, for example with respect to child protection and taking the child’s best interests into account?

Have you put in place processes to address and rectify for potential harm to children by the AI system?

Have you put in place processes to test and monitor for potential harm to children during the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system?

3. Does the AI system protect personal data relating to individuals in line with GDPR? Have you put in place processes to assess in detail the need for a data protection impact assessment, including an assessment of the necessity and proportionality of the processing operations in relation to their purpose, with respect to the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system?

Have you put in place measures envisaged to address the risks, including safeguards, security measures and mechanisms to ensure the protection of personal data with respect to the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system?

4. Does the AI system respect the freedom of expression and information and/or freedom of assembly and association?

Have you put in place processes to test and monitor for potential infringement on freedom of expression and information, and/or freedom of assembly and association, during the development, deployment and use phases of the AI system?

Have you put in place processes to address and rectify for potential infringement on freedom of expression and information, and/or freedom of assembly and association, in the AI system?” (HLEG, 2020: 5-6).

According to the latest available information, the forthcoming AI Act will also include the requirement to carry out a FRIA for certain AI systems. This is a positive development aimed at upholding fundamental rights also when AI is used.

Following the completion of the FRIA, the ALTAI contains sample questions concerning Human Agency and Autonomy, Human Oversight, Resilience to Attack and Security, General Safety, Accuracy, Reliability, Fall-back plans and Reproducibility, Privacy and Data Governance, Transparency, Traceability, Explainability, Communication, Diversity, Non-discrimination and Fairness, Avoidance of Unfair Bias, Accessibility and Universal Design, Stakeholder Participation, Societal and Environmental Well-being, Impact on Work and Skills, Impact on Society at large or Democracy, Accountability, Auditability, and Risk Management. All AI systems must be subjected to such assessments.

In relation to democracy specifically, the section of the template assessment serves to address the impact of AI on society and democracy which the HLEG states serves particular attention in relation “to the democratic processes, including not only political decision-making but also electoral contexts (e.g. when AI systems

amplify fake news, segregate the electorate, facilitate totalitarian behaviour, etc.)” (HLEG, 2020, p. 20). The Group suggests evaluating, e.g.:

- If the AI system could have a negative impact on society in general or on democracy;
- If the societal impact beyond end-users has been considered;
- If actions have been taken to minimise potential societal harms;
- If measures have been taken to ensure that the AI does not have any negative impacts on democracy (Ibid).

The HLEG also provides a general template checklist (see Table 1) which can be used by organisations, organised in the table below. This accountability exercise should be carried out by deployers and developers of AI systems on a regular basis as suggested above.

Table 1 – HLEG Trustworthy AI Assessment List (Pilot Version)

Table Source: pp. 26-31 HLEG 2019¹⁵

1. Human Agency and Oversight
a. Fundamental rights
Did you carry out a fundamental rights impact assessment where there could be a negative impact on fundamental rights?
Did you identify and document potential trade-offs made between the different principles and rights?
Could the AI system affect human autonomy by interfering with the (end) user’s decision-making process in an unintended way?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Did you consider whether the AI system should communicate to (end) users that a decision, content, advice or outcome is the result of an algorithmic decision? · In case of a chatbot or other conversational system, are the human end users made aware that they are interacting with a non-human agent?
b. Human agency
Is the AI system implemented in work and labour process? If so, did you consider the task allocation between the AI system and humans for meaningful interactions and appropriate human oversight and control?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Does the AI system enhance or augment human capabilities? · Did you take safeguards to prevent overconfidence in or overreliance on the AI system for work processes?
c. Human oversight

¹⁵ <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai>

Did you consider the appropriate level of human control for the particular AI system and use case?

- Can you describe the level of human control or involvement?
- Who is the “human in control” and what are the moments or tools for human intervention?
- Did you put in place mechanisms and measures to ensure human control or oversight?
- Did you take any measures to enable audit and to remedy issues related to governing AI autonomy?

Is there is a self-learning or autonomous AI system or use case? If so, did you put in place more specific mechanisms of control and oversight?

- Which detection and response mechanisms did you establish to assess whether something could go wrong?
- Did you ensure a stop button or procedure to safely abort an operation where needed? Does this procedure abort the process entirely, in part, or delegate control to a human?

2. Technical robustness and safety

a. Resilience to attack and security

Did you assess potential forms of attacks to which the AI system could be vulnerable?

- Did you consider different types and natures of vulnerabilities, such as data pollution, physical infrastructure, cyber-attacks?

Did you put measures or systems in place to ensure the integrity and resilience of the AI system against potential attacks?

Did you verify how your system behaves in unexpected situations and environments?

Did you consider to what degree your system could be dual-use? If so, did you take suitable preventative measures against this case (including for instance not publishing the research or deploying the system)?

b. Fallback plan and general safety

Did you ensure that your system has a sufficient fallback plan if it encounters adversarial attacks or other unexpected situations (for example technical switching procedures or asking for a human operator before proceeding)?

Did you consider the level of risk raised by the AI system in this specific use case?

- Did you put any process in place to measure and assess risks and safety?
- Did you provide the necessary information in case of a risk for human physical integrity?
- Did you consider an insurance policy to deal with potential damage from the AI system?
- Did you identify potential safety risks of (other) foreseeable uses of the technology, including accidental or malicious misuse? Is there a plan to mitigate or manage these risks?

Did you assess whether there is a probable chance that the AI system may cause damage or harm to users or third parties? Did you assess the likelihood, potential damage, impacted audience and severity?

- Did you consider the liability and consumer protection rules, and take them into account?
- Did you consider the potential impact or safety risk to the environment or to animals?
- Did your risk analysis include whether security or network problems such as cybersecurity hazards could pose safety risks or damage due to unintentional behaviour of the AI system?

Did you estimate the likely impact of a failure of your AI system when it provides wrong results, becomes unavailable, or provides societally unacceptable results (for example discrimination)?

- Did you define thresholds and did you put governance procedures in place to trigger alternative/fallback plans?
- Did you define and test fallback plans?

c. Accuracy

Did you assess what level and definition of accuracy would be required in the context of the AI system and use case?

- Did you assess how accuracy is measured and assured?
- Did you put in place measures to ensure that the data used is comprehensive and up to date?
- Did you put in place measures in place to assess whether there is a need for additional data, for example to improve accuracy or to eliminate bias?

Did you verify what harm would be caused if the AI system makes inaccurate predictions?

Did you put in place ways to measure whether your system is making an unacceptable amount of inaccurate predictions?

Did you put in place a series of steps to increase the system's accuracy?

d. Reliability and reproducibility

Did you put in place a strategy to monitor and test if the AI system is meeting the goals, purposes and intended applications?

- Did you test whether specific contexts or particular conditions need to be taken into account to ensure reproducibility?
- Did you put in place verification methods to measure and ensure different aspects of the system's reliability and reproducibility?
- Did you put in place processes to describe when an AI system fails in certain types of settings?
- Did you clearly document and operationalise these processes for the testing and verification of the reliability of AI systems?
- Did you establish mechanisms of communication to assure (end-)users of the system's reliability?

3. Privacy and data governance

a. Respect for privacy and data Protection

Depending on the use case, did you establish a mechanism allowing others to flag issues related to privacy or data protection in the AI system's processes of data collection (for training and operation) and data processing?

Did you assess the type and scope of data in your data sets (for example whether they contain personal data)?

Did you consider ways to develop the AI system or train the model without or with minimal use of potentially sensitive or personal data?

Did you build in mechanisms for notice and control over personal data depending on the use case (such as valid consent and possibility to revoke, when applicable)?

Did you take measures to enhance privacy, such as via encryption, anonymisation and aggregation?

Where a Data Privacy Officer (DPO) exists, did you involve this person at an early stage in the process?

b. Quality and integrity of data

Did you align your system with relevant standards (for example ISO, IEEE) or widely adopted protocols for daily data management and governance?

Did you establish oversight mechanisms for data collection, storage, processing and use?

Did you assess the extent to which you are in control of the quality of the external data sources used?

Did you put in place processes to ensure the quality and integrity of your data? Did you consider other processes? How are you verifying that your data sets have not been compromised or hacked?

c. Access to data

What protocols, processes and procedures did you follow to manage and ensure proper data governance?

- **Did you assess who can access users' data, and under what circumstances?**
- **Did you ensure that these persons are qualified and required to access the data, and that they have the necessary competences to understand the details of data protection policy?**
- **Did you ensure an oversight mechanism to log when, where, how, by whom and for what purpose data was accessed?**

4. Transparency

a. Traceability

- **Did you establish measures that can ensure traceability?**
 - **This could entail documenting the following methods: Methods used for designing and developing the algorithmic system:**
 - § **Rule-based AI systems: the method of programming or how the model was built;**
 - § **Learning-based AI systems; the method of training the algorithm, including which input data was gathered and selected, and how this occurred.**
 - **Methods used to test and validate the algorithmic system:**
 - § **Rule-based AI systems; the scenarios or cases used in order to test and validate;**
 - § **Learning-based model: information about the data used to test and validate.**
 - **Outcomes of the algorithmic system:**
 - § **The outcomes of or decisions taken by the algorithm, as well as potential other decisions that would result from different cases (for example, for other subgroups of users).**

b. Explainability

Did you assess:

- **to what extent the decisions and hence the outcome made by the AI system can be understood?**
- **to what degree the system's decision influences the organisation's decision-making processes?**
- **why this particular system was deployed in this specific area?**
- **what the system's business model is (for example, how does it create value for the organisation)?**

Did you ensure an explanation as to why the system took a certain choice resulting in a certain outcome that all users can understand?

Did you design the AI system with interpretability in mind from the start?

- Did you research and try to use the simplest and most interpretable model possible for the application in question?
- Did you assess whether you can analyse your training and testing data? Can you change and update this over time?
- Did you assess whether you can examine interpretability after the model's training and development, or whether you have access to the internal workflow of the model?

c. Communication

Did you communicate to (end-)users – through a disclaimer or any other means – that they are interacting with an AI system and not with another human? Did you label your AI system as such?

Did you establish mechanisms to inform (end-)users on the reasons and criteria behind the AI system's outcomes?

- Did you communicate this clearly and intelligibly to the intended audience?
- Did you establish processes that consider users' feedback and use this to adapt the system?
- Did you communicate around potential or perceived risks, such as bias?
- Depending on the use case, did you consider communication and transparency towards other audiences, third parties or the general public?

Did you clarify the purpose of the AI system and who or what may benefit from the product/service?

- Did you specify usage scenarios for the product and clearly communicate these to ensure that it is understandable and appropriate for the intended audience?
- Depending on the use case, did you think about human psychology and potential limitations, such as risk of confusion, confirmation bias or cognitive fatigue?

Did you clearly communicate characteristics, limitations and potential shortcomings of the AI system?

- In case of the system's development: to whoever is deploying it into a product or service?
- In case of the system's deployment: to the (end-)user or consumer?

5. Diversity, non-discrimination and fairness

a. Unfair bias avoidance

Did you establish a strategy or a set of procedures to avoid creating or reinforcing unfair bias in the AI system, both regarding the use of input data as well as for the algorithm design?

- Did you assess and acknowledge the possible limitations stemming from the composition of the used data sets?
- Did you consider diversity and representativeness of users in the data? Did you test for specific populations or problematic use cases?
- Did you research and use available technical tools to improve your understanding of the data, model and performance?
- Did you put in place processes to test and monitor for potential biases during the development, deployment and use phase of the system?

Depending on the use case, did you ensure a mechanism that allows others to flag issues related to bias, discrimination or poor performance of the AI system?

- Did you establish clear steps and ways of communicating on how and to whom such issues can be raised?
- Did you consider others, potentially indirectly affected by the AI system, in addition to the (end)- users?

Did you assess whether there is any possible decision variability that can occur under the same conditions?

- If so, did you consider what the possible causes of this could be?
- In case of variability, did you establish a measurement or assessment mechanism of the potential impact of such variability on fundamental rights?

Did you ensure an adequate working definition of “fairness” that you apply in designing AI systems?

- Is your definition commonly used? Did you consider other definitions before choosing this one?
- Did you ensure a quantitative analysis or metrics to measure and test the applied definition of fairness?
- Did you establish mechanisms to ensure fairness in your AI systems? Did you consider other potential mechanisms?

b. Accessibility and universal design

Did you ensure that the AI system accommodates a wide range of individual preferences and abilities?

- Did you assess whether the AI system is usable by those with special needs or disabilities or those at risk of exclusion? How was this designed into the system and how is it verified?
- Did you ensure that information about the AI system is accessible also to users of assistive technologies?
- Did you involve or consult this community during the development phase of the AI system?

Did you take the impact of your AI system on the potential user audience into account?

- Did you assess whether the team involved in building the AI system is representative of your target user audience? Is it representative of the wider population, considering also of other groups who might tangentially be impacted?
- Did you assess whether there could be persons or groups who might be disproportionately affected by negative implications?
- Did you get feedback from other teams or groups that represent different backgrounds and experiences?

c. Stakeholder participation

Did you consider a mechanism to include the participation of different stakeholders in the AI system’s development and use?

Did you pave the way for the introduction of the AI system in your organisation by informing and involving impacted workers and their representatives in advance?

6. Societal and environmental well-being

a. Sustainable and environmentally friendly AI

Did you establish mechanisms to measure the environmental impact of the AI system’s development, deployment and use (for example the type of energy used by the data centres)?

Did you ensure measures to reduce the environmental impact of your AI system’s life cycle?

b. Social impact

In case the AI system interacts directly with humans:

- **Did you assess whether the AI system encourages humans to develop attachment and empathy towards the system?**
- **Did you ensure that the AI system clearly signals that its social interaction is simulated and that it has no capacities of “understanding” and “feeling”?**

Did you ensure that the social impacts of the AI system are well understood? For example, did you assess whether there is a risk of job loss or de-skilling of the workforce? What steps have been taken to counteract such risks?

c. Society and democracy

Did you assess the broader societal impact of the AI system’s use beyond the individual (end-)user, such as potentially indirectly affected stakeholders?

7. Accountability

a. Auditability

Did you establish mechanisms that facilitate the system’s auditability, such as ensuring traceability and logging of the AI system’s processes and outcomes?

Did you ensure, in applications affecting fundamental rights (including safety-critical applications) that the AI system can be audited independently?

b. Minimising and reporting negative Impact

Did you carry out a risk or impact assessment of the AI system, which takes into account different stakeholders that are (in)directly affected?

Did you provide training and education to help develop accountability practices?

- **Which workers or branches of the team are involved? Does it go beyond the development phase?**
- **Do these trainings also teach the potential legal framework applicable to the AI system?**
- **Did you consider establishing an ‘ethical AI review board’ or a similar mechanism to discuss overall accountability and ethics practices, including potentially unclear grey areas?**

Did you foresee any kind of external guidance or put in place auditing processes to oversee ethics and accountability, in addition to internal initiatives?

Did you establish processes for third parties (e.g. suppliers, consumers, distributors/vendors) or workers to report potential vulnerabilities, risks or biases in the AI system?

c. Documenting trade-offs

Did you establish a mechanism to identify relevant interests and values implicated by the AI system and potential trade-offs between them?

How do you decide on such trade-offs? Did you ensure that the trade-off decision was documented?

d. Ability to redress

Did you establish an adequate set of mechanisms that allows for redress in case of the occurrence of any harm or adverse impact?

Did you put mechanisms in place both to provide information to (end-)users/third parties about opportunities for redress?

3.1.2.4 Challenges and Opportunities

The existing and proposed legislation governing AI, big data and frontier technologies may bring about challenges and opportunities in fostering democracy. For instance, the “EU Brussels effect” may be an opportunity towards fostering democracy. The “EU Brussels effect” allows Europe to transplant high standards globally. In general, if the EU through its current and proposed legislation sets a high standard for fostering democracy, this may lead to the fight towards achieving similar or higher levels of standards. Effective EU rules will thus perpetuate the Brussels effect.

Regulatory compliance with the current and proposed legislation may be a challenge for companies, especially small ones. While regulatory compliance may seem like a burden, it plays a crucial role in protecting consumers and mitigating the possible risks that may be posed on the use of frontier technologies. Political pressure may also play a significant role in strengthening democracy as the citizens seek to influence government policies and decisions in favour of the public interest. The political pressure thus leads to the development of legislation that protects the rights of citizens and ultimately fosters democracy.

3.2 Profiling and Targeting under the EU Legal Framework

Profiling as defined in Article 4(4) of the GDPR is any form of automated processing of personal data which consists of the use of personal data to evaluate certain personal aspects relating to a natural person, and in particular, to analyse or predict aspects which concern their performance at work, economic situation, health, interests, personal preferences, reliability, behaviour, location or movements. Profiling is a common data processing activity which may adversely affect the rights and freedoms of data subjects and may also be used for political purposes.¹⁶

Profiling may pose a challenge in democracy due to the fact that the decision-making process creates unbalanced distribution among citizens on one side and government and organisations and companies on the other side. Essentially, decisions based on automated profiling techniques may not allow the citizens to challenge the reasoning behind the process and this may have a negative impact on effective participation in a democracy (Ferraris, Valeria, et al, 2013).

The French Data Protection Authority defines targeted advertising as a technique that aims to identify people in order to deliver specific advertising messages to them based on their individual characteristics (French Data Protection Authority (CNIL), n.p.). Government and entity practices that are incentivized by target advertising models may endanger human rights indirectly or contribute to the violation of rights of a group of people. The risks caused are based on an initial violation of privacy of individuals or citizens that occurs in the targeted advertising service (Ranking Digital Rights, 2019:2a). For example, targeted political advertising

¹⁶ For more on profiling see section 2 in Module D.

for citizens may hinder the citizens freedom of expression and information by denying the citizens the right to freely elect and choose their representatives Ranking Digital Rights, 2019:2b.¹⁷

3.2.1 Profiling and Targeted Advertising

As discussed in Module D, targeted advertising uses data about individuals to select and display advertisements or other forms of commercial content and personal data is obtained either directly or indirectly from the data subjects. The personal data that has been collected are processed for the purpose of user profiling, deriving analytics, machine learning, and cognitive computing technologies (Regulating targeted and behavioural advertising in digital services, 2021). Individuals can thus be grouped according to their interests, attitudes and behaviour. This section outlines the ways that legal frameworks and regulation concerning profiling and targeted advertising intersect with individuals' freedoms.

Article 8(2) of the Charter outlines consent as a legal basis for the processing of personal data. Similarly, as outlined above, the GDPR outlines the conditions of consent to be a freely given, specific, informed, and unambiguous indication of data subjects' wishes, given through a statement or a clear affirmative action. The ePrivacy Directive also requires users' consent for placing of cookies and other tracking devices on their terminal.

On the one hand, the Digital Markets Act (DMA) that aims to ensure that gatekeepers act fairly online provides that gatekeeper platforms may no longer track end users outside of the gatekeepers' core platform service for the purpose of targeted advertising, without effective consent having been granted (Article 5(2) DMA). It also places an obligation for periodical auditing of gatekeepers' profiling techniques to ensure transparency. On the other hand, the Digital Services Act (DSA) requires platforms to be transparent in their content moderation and lays down rules on transparency of content moderation. The European Commission affirmed that the DSA protects freedom of expression, including freedom and pluralism of the media (European Commission, 2023a). The legislation strikes a balance between combating illegal content and safeguarding freedom of expression and information online. This also relates to the protection from government interference in people's freedom of expression and information (European Commission, 2023b).

The EDPB Guidelines on the targeting of social media users states that, there are two legal bases which could theoretically justify the processing that supports the targeting of social media users i.e., data subject's consent or legitimate interest. The EDPB noted that in cases where a data controller seeks to rely on legitimate interest, the duties of transparency and the right to object need to be carefully considered. Furthermore, data subjects should be given the opportunity to object to the processing of their data for targeted purposes before the processing is initiated (EDPB Guidelines 8/2020 on the targeting of social media users, 2020).

There is a huge risk for discrimination when it comes to targeted advertising for example, job offers can directly exclude individuals from material opportunities. On the flip side, it can also facilitate deliberate inclusion targeting vulnerable groups with products such as gambling and payday loans (Griffin, 2022).

¹⁷ For more on political targeted advertising see module D.

3.2.1.1 Political Advertising

In 2020, as part of the European Democracy Plan, the European Commission announced an initiative to complement the DSA's rules on online advertising by way of a proposal concerning sponsored political advertising (COM(2021) 731 final) (European Parliament, 2023a). The proposal was presented at the end of 2021 and specifically aims to foster more transparency in this area. The Proposal for a Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the transparency and targeting of political advertising (COM(2021) 731 final) aims to establish clear and harmonised rules to provide transparency in political advertising (COM(2021) 731 final).

Wojciech Wiewiórowski, the European Data Protection Supervisor, has underlined that “Political communication is essential for citizens, political parties and candidates in order to fully participate in democratic life. To preserve our democracy, we also need strong rules to combat disinformation, voter manipulation and interference with our elections. We need to do more if we want to tackle the many risks surrounding the use of targeting and amplification techniques for political purposes” (EDPS, 2022). In order to serve political advertisements to individuals, both data provided directly by individuals and data which is acquired from their online activities are used (European Parliament, 2023b). The political advertisement targeting process “has been observed to have specific negative effects on citizens’ rights including their freedoms of opinion and of information, to make political decisions and exercise their voting rights” (European Parliament, 2023c).

Political advertising indeed has a significant potential to influence democratic processes. In order to protect democracy, the EDPS has called for more restrictions to be put on the categories of data which may be used for political advertising purposes (European Parliament, 2023d). The EDPS’ Opinion 2/2022 which critiques the Proposed Regulation, appreciates the essential nature of political communication for democracy and stresses the interdependency between the right to privacy established in Article 7 of the Charter and the right to data protection under Article 8 of the Charter (EDPS, 2022:2a). At the same time, the Opinion recalls the numerous risks which are posed by such activities and calls for a “full ban of microtargeting for political purposes” and the introduction of “further restrictions on the categories of data that may be processed for the purposes of political advertising, including targeting and amplification, in particular prohibiting targeted advertising based on pervasive tracking” (EDPS, 2022:2b).

The proposed Regulation complements the GDPR and the DSA but goes further than the DSA in “expand(ing) the categories of information to be disclosed in the context of political advertising as well as the scope of the relevant service providers concerned” (EDPS, 2022:5a). Thus, while the DSA provides for transparency requirements for online platforms, the proposed Regulation “seeks to cover the entire spectrum of political advertising publishes” (EDPS, 2022:5a).

Microtargeting has been used to adversely affect democratic processes in the past. For instance, during the 2016 US elections, it was discovered that “Russian operatives” utilised Facebook to specifically target Black Americans with the aim of dissuading them from voting (New York Times, 2023a). Similarly, Donald Trump’s political campaign made significant use of targeting to rally voters, serving them with “inflammatory messages” (New York Times, 2023b). More recently in Europe, Orbán “campaign sent tailored

advertisements to people they already had data on, as well as sending targeted advertisements according to gender, in which advertisements discussing the war in Ukraine were sent only to male Facebook users” (EDRi, 2023).

As pointed out by EDRi, politicians make use of special category data, such as ethnicity, religion, health information, and sexual orientation “to target different parts of the population with different messages. If they say different things to different voters, it allows them to spread misinformation to fire up their supporters and deter people from going to the polls” (EDRi, 2023b). In order to ensure that democratic processes and specifically elections are safeguarded in the future, it is paramount that the legislative process concerning the

On 6 November 2023 a political agreement was reached on the proposed Regulation of the European Parliament and of the Council on the transparency and targeting of political advertising (European Parliament Legislative Train Schedule, 2023a). According to the European Parliament’s Legislative Train, the law will prohibit profiling with special categories of personal data, restrict non-EU entities financing political ads within the EU, and establish a dedicated database to examine political advertisements (European Parliament Legislative Train Schedule, 2023b). It is highly necessary that the Regulation is urgently adopted so as to protect EU democratic processes.

3.2.1.2 Challenges and Opportunities

Profiling and targeted advertising may create challenges and opportunities for fostering democracy. For example, microtargeting has allowed advertisers to discriminate in a manner that is difficult for regulators to catch (New York Times, 2023a). Using language that suggests that job offers, housing or credit opportunities are being offered to people of certain race, gender, age or other protected categories is illegal (New York Times, 2023b). A new study showed that targeted advertisements shown to a set of participants were pitching more expensive products from lower-quality vendors than similar products that showed up during a simple web-search (New York Times, 2023c). Advertisers can thus easily hide their preferences in targeted advertising through the algorithm and this has been demonstrated repeatedly by Facebook which has enabled discriminatory advertisement (Faife, et al., 2021).

Targeted advertising evidently poses a threat to democracy, and this may be demonstrated in the verified instance of Russian interference in the 2016 United States presidential elections. The Democratic National Committee and its cyber response team made a public announcement that Russian hackers had compromised its computer network (Federal Bureau of Investigation, n.p.). Additional pertinent instances within the EU include the political advertising that is widely used by the Chinese platform, TikTok (China Observers in Central and Eastern Europe, 2023). This may pose a threat to democracy through manipulation campaigns.

3.3 Facial Recognition

Facial recognition technologies (FRTs) are biometric systems that are widely used in the EU context. They provide a very intrusive surveillance power as algorithmic technologies. Debate around FRTs has fuelled the discussion of the proposed AI Act (Giuseppe Mobilo, 2023a). The EDPS defines Facial Emotion Recognition (FER) as “a technology that analyses facial expressions from both static images and videos in order to reveal information on one’s emotional state (EDPS, 2021a).” The EDPS further recognizes that the complexity of facial expressions and the potential use of the technology in any context, and the involvement of new technologies such as AI poses potential risks (EDPS, 2021b).

There will be rules on the use of FRTs under the proposed AI Act in that it will lay down exceptions for the use of “real time” remote biometric identification in publicly accessible spaces for law enforcement. This section will be updated in the next deliverable as some changes may still occur given the current status of the proposed AI Act. FRT systems have the capability of preventing severe crimes and detecting suspects. However, such systems often provide inaccurate or biased results which may ultimately pose a risk to the fundamental rights and freedoms of citizens (Internet Policy Review, 2023).

3.3.1 Relevant Guidelines on Facial Recognition

EU DPAs also have shown their scepticism about facial recognition systems. For example, the Italian data protection authority imposed a data protection fine of EUR 20 million on Clearview AI, a US company offering facial recognition solutions. The Facial Emotion Recognition journal by the EDPS is relevant in identifying some of the risks of using facial recognition and artificial intelligence. It mentions that if the training data is not diverse enough, the technology might be biased against a group of people that is not represented (Facial Emotion Recognition-EDPS, 2021b). It also states that public surveillance cameras may capture expressions during their use and in these situations, transparency issues concerning both the collection and the further processing of personal data may arise.

In the subsequent sections, we will analyse the main elements of the EDPB Guidelines on facial recognition in the area of law enforcement and also the Convention 108 Guidelines on Facial Recognition.

3.3.1.1 EDPB Guidelines on Facial Recognition

The EDPB adopted a final version of its Guidelines on facial recognition in the area of law enforcement. Generally, the guidelines serve as a guidance to EU and state legislators, and also law enforcement authorities in the implementation and use of FRTs. The Guidelines emphasise that the Facial recognition tools should only be used in compliance with the Law Enforcement Directive (LED). Furthermore, such tools should only be used if necessary and proportionate as per the Charter (Guidelines 05/2022 on the use of facial recognition technology in the area of law enforcement, 2023a)

The Guidelines also provide that the legal basis must be clear in terms to give citizens an adequate indication on the conditions and circumstances in which authorities may resort to any measures relating to the collection of data and secret surveillance. The Guidelines also recognize that law enforcement authorities have sovereign powers and, FRT faces the risk of interfering with fundamental rights, also beyond the right to protection of personal data and this may have an overall effect on the citizens social and democratic political stability. The application of FRT by enforcement authorities has significant implications on individuals and on groups of people, including minorities. These Guidelines further recognize that the implications have considerable effects on the way we live together and on our social and democratic political stability (Guidelines 05/2022 on the use of facial recognition technology in the area of law enforcement, 2023b). The data of citizens thus has to be processed in a manner that guarantees the effectiveness of the EU data protection rules and principles.

3.3.1.2 The CoE 108 on Facial Recognition

The Convention 108 Guidelines on Facial Recognition outline a set of guidelines that governments, facial recognition developers, manufacturers, service providers and entities using FRTs should apply in order to guarantee that such technology does not adversely affect the human dignity, human rights and fundamental freedoms of citizens, including their right to protection of personal data (The Convention 108 Guidelines on Facial Recognition, 2021a).

Legislators and decision makers need to take into consideration the lawfulness of processing when considering the prohibition of processing using FRTs and need to involve supervisory authorities during the legislative process. The Guidelines stipulate that developers, manufactures and service providers need to ensure the quality of data and algorithms in the use of FRT to avoid adverse effects on individuals. They need to guarantee the reliability of the tools used and respect the rights of data subjects. Entities using FRTs need to ensure that the data security principle is guaranteed. This means that strong security measures should be implemented to protect facial recognition data and image sets against loss and unauthorised access (The Convention 108 Guidelines on Facial Recognition, 2021b).

The use of live FRT that is coupled with the risk towards human rights and freedoms should be subject to a democratic debate prior to its use. These rights of data subject may only be restricted when such limitation is provided for by law, it respects the essence of the fundamental rights and freedoms and constitutes a necessary and proportionate measure in a democratic society for specific legitimate purposes (The Convention 108 Guidelines on Facial Recognition, 2021c).

3.3.1.3 Challenges and Opportunities

The use of FRTs and AI in general can have a significant impact both on individuals and on society as a whole. Extremely high-risk scenarios need to be defined where the rights and freedoms of individuals may be adversely impacted. Some of the challenges may result in the fairness of the algorithm system. The accuracy of the facial recognition system may lead to discrimination on grounds such as skin colour and ethnic origin.

Cultural differences may influence the level of expression of some emotions while at the same time, some algorithms may be biased against certain expressions of emotions (Facial Emotion Recognition-EDPS, 2021c). This may have serious implications such as the inability to use certain services by a certain group due to the errors in detecting the correct emotional state.

Undeniably, the use of FRTs has posed certain opportunities such as being an enabler for efficient security, public order and border control. If the guidelines on FRT are taken into consideration, it will lead to the effective deployment of such technologies and ultimately foster democracy where there is public order and efficient security for the citizens.

3.4 Conclusions

This section has provided an analysis of how AI, big data and frontier technologies impact rights from the data protection and general human rights perspective. It has provided a legal and regulatory analysis of currently applicable and proposed legislation concerning frontier technologies, which includes knowledge technologies, as well as the legal framework applicable to profiling and targeted advertising, and in particular, facial recognition and political advertising. Additionally, it has provided an analysis of the risks for data transfers to negatively impact democracy and fundamental rights and highlight the risks or challenges and opportunities in terms of rights and democracy with respect to frontier technologies.

4 Advancement of the State of the Art

The risks conceptualised in this module will form the basis for a social risk toolkit developed in later versions in task 4.3. The theory and analysis in this version of the module will influence the ways that risks are identified, avoided, mitigated, and understood in the social risk toolkit as a whole. This will advance the state of the art by providing guidance for academics, CSOs, policymakers, and technologists involved in the development and use of knowledge technologies.

Moreover, in the next version of the deliverable, we will have an update on the proposed legislation concerning frontier technologies and provide an analysis of more guidelines relating to AI including the UN World Economic and Social Survey 2018 on Frontier Technologies for Sustainable Development and the Technology and Innovation Report 2021 from the UN Conference.

5 Conclusion

This version of Module E is the culmination of research activity undertaken in task 4.1. This version provides a conceptual overview of the risks to individuals' freedom of speech and action from the development and use of knowledge technologies. The risks contained within this version will form a later social risk toolkit with

actionable guidance. This version also surveys existing and emerging legislation and regulations in respect to the ways knowledge technologies may limit individuals' freedom of speech and action.

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No	Description/Link
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R190	Zang, D. (2022) Who Owns Data? Constitutional Division in Cyberspace. <i>Transnat'l L. & Contemp. Probs.</i> , 32: 109.
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R192	Zittrain, J., Ammori, M. and Heins, M. (2014) <i>Engineering an election</i> , <i>Harvard Law Review</i> . Available at: https://harvardlawreview.org/2014/06/engineering-an-election/

Appendix I. Table of AI Frameworks

Name of Framework	Reference n.	Author	Origin (i.e., Pan European, USA, Brazil, etc.)	Type (legal, ethics, policy, etc.)	Date	Main points / Relevance for Client	Link
Preliminary Opinion of the European Data Protection Supervisor Privacy and competitiveness in the age of big data: The interplay between data protection, competition law and consumer protection in the Digital Economy	1	The European Data Protection Supervisor	European	Legal	March 2014	It acknowledges that, in certain markets, consumers may consider a more privacy-friendly service to be of better quality than a service which has an unclear or opaque privacy policy. In the provision of legal and medical services, private banking, security services, and exclusive luxury resorts, businesses typically compete on protecting privacy. It is reasonable to assume that, in such competitive markets, a failure by one company to respect data protection would damage their market power. To a much more limited extent, some internet search services aim to differentiate on privacy.	https://edps.europa.eu/sites/edp/files/publication/14-03-26_competition_law_big_data_en.pdf

Opinion 8/2014 on the on Recent Developments on the Internet of Things	2	Article 29 Data Protection Working Party	European	Legal	16 September 2014	It identifies the main data protection risks that lie within the ecosystem of the IoT before providing guidance on how the EU legal framework should be applied in this context.	https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/documentation/opinion-recommendation/files/2014/wp223_en.pdf
Statement on Statement of the WP29 on the impact of the development of big data on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of their personal data in the EU	3	Article 29 Data Protection Working Party	European	Legal	16 September 2014	The statement acknowledged that complying with this framework is a key element in creating and keeping the trust which any stakeholder needs in order to develop a stable business model that is based on the processing of such data. It also believes that compliance with this framework and investment in privacy-friendly solutions is essential to ensure fair and effective competition between economic players on the relevant markets.	https://ec.europa.eu/justice/article-29/documentation/opinion-recommendation/files/2014/wp221_en.pdf
Opinion 4/2015 Towards a new digital ethics	4	The European Data Protection Supervisor	European	Ethics	11 September 2015	The opinion highlights specific trends which - though obviously not exhaustive (may include AI) raise the most important ethical and practical questions for the application of data protection principles.	https://edps.europa.eu/sites/edp/files/publication/15-09-11_data_ethics_en.pdf

Opinion 7/2015 Meeting the challenges of big data. A call for transparency, user control, data protection by design and accountability.	5	The European Data Protection Supervisor	European	Legal	19 November 2015	It outlines the steps on how to put privacy by design and accountability among other principles in practice.	https://edps.europa.eu/sites/edp/files/publication/15-11-19_big_data_en.pdf
EDPS Opinion on coherent enforcement of fundamental rights in the age of big data Opinion 8/2016	6	The European Data Protection Supervisor	European	Legal	23 September 2016	It outlines the ways in which privacy and privacy-enhancing technologies may be fostered as a competitive advantage.	https://edps.europa.eu/sites/edp/files/publication/16-09-23_bigdata_opinion_en.pdf
Preparing for the future of Artificial Intelligence	7	Executive Office of the President of the United States	US	Report	October 2016	It provides a case study scenario on the use of AI in autonomous vehicles and aircraft. It highlights the importance of fairness, safety and governance in AI.	https://obamawhitehouse.archives.gov/sites/default/files/whitehouse_files/microsites/ostp/NSTC/preparing_for_the_future_of_ai.pdf

EDPS Opinion on Personal Information Management Systems	8	The European Data Protection Supervisor	European	Legal	20 October 2016	It outlines the opportunities towards the full implementation of the GDPR and outlines how PIMS can support data protection principles.	https://edps.europa.eu/sites/edp/files/publication/16-10-20_pims_opinion_en.pdf
An ethical approach to fundamental rights	9	Giovanni Buttarelli	European	Ethics	1 December 2016	The report outlines how to integrate integrity of our values while embracing the benefits of new technologies.	https://edps.europa.eu/press-publications/press-news/blog/ethical-approach-fundamental-rights_en
Guidelines on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data in a world of big data	10	Council of Europe	European	Policy	23 January 2017	The Guidelines acknowledge the need to balance all interests concerned in the processing of personal data, and in particular where information is used for predictive purposes in decision-making processes.	https://rm.coe.int/16806ebe7a

EDPS Ethics Advisory Group 2018 Report	11	EDPS Ethics Advisory Group	European	Ethics	2018	The report identifies and clarifies some of the ethical questions that emerge in the application of data protection regulations to the new forms of data collection and processing and to the new economy that has rapidly formed around it.	https://edps.europa.eu/sites/edp/files/publication/18-01-25_eag_report_en.pdf
Guidelines on Automated individual decision-making and Profiling for the purposes of Regulation 2016/679	12	Article 29 Data Protection Working Party	European	Legal	Last Revised and adopted on 6 February 2018	The Guidelines outline the relevant principles for profiling and automated decision making as well as good practice recommendations.	file:///C:/Users/WendyKuyoh/Downloads/wp251rev_01_en_A754F3E1-FB46-9E76-C0A919864E4B6641_49826.pdf
Preliminary Opinion on Privacy by Design Opinion 5/2018	13	The European Data Protection Supervisor	European	Legal	31 May 2018	The Opinion recognizes Privacy by design as a landmark for values driven technology development.	https://edps.europa.eu/sites/edp/files/publication/18-05-31_preliminary_opinion_on_privacy_by_design_en_0.pdf

<p>Summary of outcomes in the Public Consultation on Digital Ethics</p>	<p>14</p>	<p>The European Data Protection Supervisor</p>	<p>European</p>	<p>Ethics</p>	<p>25 September 2018</p>	<p>The EDPS Public Consultation on Digital Ethics successfully instigated, and proved demand for defining a path into an ethical digital future that re-affirms and protects the longstanding European culture of values and rights.</p>	<p>https://edps.europa.eu/sites/edp/files/publication/18-09-25_edps_publicconsultationdigitaethics_summary_en.pdf</p>
<p>Universal Guidelines for Artificial Intelligence</p>	<p>15</p>	<p>The Public Voice</p>	<p>Belgium</p>	<p>Ethics</p>	<p>23 October 2018</p>	<p>The guidelines outline the primary responsibility for AI systems which include: Right to transparency, right to human determination, identification obligation, fairness and accuracy.</p>	<p>https://thepublicvoice.org/ai-universal-guidelines/#:~:text=An%20AI%20system%20should%20be,%2C%20Reliability%2C%20and%20Validity%20Obligations.</p>

<p>Human rights in the age of Artificial Intelligence</p>	<p>16</p>	<p>Access Now</p>	<p>United States</p>	<p>Report</p>	<p>November 2018</p>	<p>The report is a preliminary scoping of the intersection of artificial intelligence and human rights. It looks at how different artificial intelligence systems are used in the world today and ways in which they can both help or harm society. Turning to human rights, it also looks at the role human rights law can play in the development of artificial intelligence, including the interplay between these fundamental rights and ethics. Then, looking at widely adopted human rights instruments, it highlights the ways current and foreseeable uses of artificial intelligence can interfere with a broad range of human rights. Finally, it offers a list of recommendations for stakeholders to protect those rights.</p>	<p>https://www.accessnow.org/wp-content/uploads/2018/11/AI-and-Human-Rights.pdf</p>
<p>CEPEJ European Ethical Charter on the use of artificial intelligence (AI) in judicial systems and their environment</p>	<p>17</p>	<p>European Commission for the Efficiency of Justice (CEPEJ)</p>	<p>Council of Europe</p>	<p>Policy</p>	<p>December 2018</p>	<p>It presents a set of principles that are helpful in the development of AI policies.</p>	<p>https://www.coe.int/en/web/cepej/cepej-european-ethical-charter-on-the-use-of-artificial-intelligence-ai-in-judicial-systems-</p>

							and-their-environment#:~:text=The%20CEPEJ's%20view%20as%20set,onn%20Human%20Rights%20(ECHR)%20and
Artificial Intelligence Principles & Ethics	18	Digital Dubai	United Arab Emirates	Ethics	January 2019	The toolkit offers guidance in understanding how AI can be used responsibly.	https://www.digitaldubai.ae/initiatives/ai-principles-ethics#:~:text=The%20Dubai%20AI%20Principles%20and,abide%20by%20the%20guidance%20provided.
Report on the International Conference of Data Protection and Privacy Commissioners: Debating Ethics – Dignity and	19	The European Data Protection Supervisor	European	Ethics	28 January 2019	The report acknowledges that privacy is one of the most basic of human needs, and we are in the business of ensuring that it is respected, irrespective of the directions the winds of political and technological change may be blowing at any given time.	https://edps.europa.eu/sites/default/files/publication/19-01-28_icdppc_2018_report_final_en.pdf

Respect in Data Driven Life							
White Paper on Artificial Intelligence: a European approach to excellence and trust	20	European Commission	European	Policy	19 February 2019	This paper acknowledges and outlines the risk involved in the use of AI, including on personal data and privacy protection as well as on non-discrimination. It also acknowledges the gaps in the legislative framework and suggests the possible adjustments to it. The Paper is relevant in highlighting the relevant compliance and enforcement measures that ought to be implemented when designing and implementing a system.	https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2020-02/commission-white-paper-artificial-intelligence-feb2020_en.pdf
Social Principles of Human-centric AI	21	Council for Science, Technology	Japan	Ethics	March 2019	The document presents a set of relevant issues to look at in the development and implementation of AI.	https://www.cas.go.jp/jp/seisaku/jinkouchinou/pdf/humancentricai.pdf

		and Innovation					
OECD.AI Policy Observatory Recommendation of the Council on Artificial Intelligence	22	OECD	Global	Policy	22 May 2019	<p>The Recommendation identifies five complementary values-based principles for the responsible stewardship of trustworthy AI and calls on AI actors to promote and implement them: inclusive growth, sustainable development and well-being;</p> <p>human-centred values and fairness;</p> <p>transparency and explainability;</p> <p>robustness, security and safety; and accountability.</p>	https://legalinstruments.oecd.org/en/instruments/oecd-legal-0449#:~:text=The%20OECD%20Recommendation%20on%20AI,governments%20in%20their%20implementation%20efforts.
Ethics guidelines for trustworthy AI	23	HLEG AI	European	Ethics	8 April 2019	<p>The Guidelines put forward a set of 7 key requirements that AI systems should meet in order to be deemed trustworthy. It outlines a specific assessment list that aims to help verify the application of each of the key requirements.</p>	https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ethics-guidelines-trustworthy-ai

<p>Governance Principles for a New Generation of AI</p>	<p>24</p>	<p>China’s Ministry of Science and Technology (English provided by the Library of Congress)</p>	<p>China</p>	<p>Guideline</p>	<p>June 2019</p>	<p>The following eight principles of AI governance are proposed:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> harmony and friendliness; fairness and justice; inclusiveness and sharing; respect for privacy; security and controllability; shared responsibility; open cooperation; and agile governance. 	<p>https://www.loc.gov/item/global-legal-monitor/2019-09-09/china-ai-governance-principles-released/#:~:text=The%20AI%20Governance%20Principles%20provide,and%20controllable%3B%20promote%20economically%2C%20socially</p>
<p>Policy and investment recommendations for trustworthy Artificial Intelligence</p>	<p>25</p>	<p>HLEG AI</p>	<p>European</p>	<p>Ethics</p>	<p>26 June 2019</p>	<p>The policy provides tips on how to use trustworthy AI to build a positive impact in Europe with a specific focus on: Humans and society, the private sector, the public sector and research and academia.</p>	<p>https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/policy-and-investment-recommendations-trustworthy-artificial-intelligence</p>

<p>The French National Strategy on Artificial Intelligence: Towards a French and European Strategy</p>	<p>26</p>	<p>Towards Data Science</p>	<p>France</p>	<p>Ethics</p>	<p>15 January 2020</p>	<p>The document is relevant in highlighting the ethical considerations of AI. Some of the ethical considerations include:</p> <p>Explaining machine-learning algorithms;</p> <p>Facilitating an audit in AI systems;</p> <p>Making the staff aware of the ethical issues involved in the development of AI technologies; and</p> <p>Consideration of the role of automation in human decisions.</p>	<p>https://towardsdata-science.com/the-french-national-strategy-on-artificial-intelligence-c8c8fcfdace1</p>
<p>GDPR Compliance of processing that embed Artificial Intelligence</p>	<p>27</p>	<p>Spanish Data Protection Authority (AEPD)</p>	<p>Spain</p>	<p>Legal</p>	<p>February 2020</p>	<p>The document gives an introduction to the AI framework and data protection, the roles, relationships and responsibilities of the various parties and the applicable compliance measures.</p>	<p>https://www.aepd.es/documento/ads/es/documento/ads/educacion-rgpd-ia-en.pdf</p>
<p>The final Assessment List for Trustworthy AI (ALTAI)</p>	<p>28</p>	<p>HLEG AI</p>	<p>European</p>	<p>Ethics</p>	<p>17 July 2020</p>	<p>The Guidelines lay down the key requirements for a trustworthy AI based on seven key requirements including: privacy and data governance.</p>	<p>https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/assessment-list-trustworthy-artificial-</p>

							intelligence-ai-self-assessment This new list is available as a prototype web based tool and in PDF format .
Sectoral Considerations on the Policy and Investment Recommendations	29	HLEG AI	European	Ethics and Law	23 July 2020	The report represents how to best enable a thriving European environment for Trustworthy AI.	https://futurium.ec.europa.eu/en/european-ai-alliance/document/ai-hleg-sectoral-considerations-policy-and-investment-recommendations-trustworthy-ai

<p>Audit requirements for personal data processing requirements involving AI</p>	<p>30</p>	<p>Spanish Data Protection Authority (AEPD)</p>	<p>European</p>	<p>Policy</p>	<p>January 2021</p>	<p>This document is relevant for controllers who are in charge of auditing processing activities including AI-based components, as well as processors or developers who wish to provide guarantees with regard to their products and solutions, Data Protection Officers in charge of supervising specific processing activities and acting as advisers to controllers, and audit teams in charge of assessing such activities.</p>	<p>https://www.aepd.es/documento/requisitos-auditorias-tratamientos-incluyan-ia-en.pdf#:~:text=The%20criteria%20that%20must%20guide,s torage%20limitation%2C%20integrity%20and%20confidentiality%2C</p>
<p>Coordinated Plan on Artificial Intelligence</p>	<p>31</p>	<p>European Commission</p>	<p>European</p>	<p>Policy</p>	<p>21 April 2021</p>	<p>The Coordinated Plan on AI (2021) puts forward EU measures on supporting innovation and enabling conditions, such as access to data and computing infrastructure, promoting the development and deployment of trustworthy AI solutions, training and skills development, as well as promoting the EU's value-based approach to AI on the global stage.</p>	<p>https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/coordinated-plan-artificial-intelligence-2021-review</p>

AEPD-EDPS Joint Paper- 10 Misunderstandings about Machine Learning	32	AEPD & EDPS	European	Joint Paper	20 September 2022	The paper clarifies general misunderstandings about machine learning systems and gives the corresponding facts to the misunderstandings.	https://edps.europa.eu/system/files/2022-09/22-09-20_10-misunderstandings-on-machine-learning_en.pdf
Self-assessment guide to artificial intelligence (AI) systems	33	French Data Protection Authority (CNIL)	France	Guideline	21 September 2022	The guide provides a reminder of the main data protection issues in the most commonly encountered scenarios.	https://www.cnil.fr/en/self-assessment-guide-artificial-intelligence-ai-systems

<p>Blueprint for an AI Bill of Rights</p>	<p>34</p>	<p>White House Office of Science and Technology Policy</p>	<p>USA</p>	<p>Legal</p>	<p>October 2022</p>	<p>This blueprint mentions the fact that Algorithms used in hiring and credit decisions have been found to reflect and reproduce existing unwanted inequities or embed new harmful bias and discrimination. It highlights the principle of data protection as one of the 5 principles in the use and design of data protection. The Blueprint for an AI Bill of Rights lays out five core protections to which the American public should be entitled:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Safe and Effective Systems: You should be protected from unsafe or ineffective systems. ● Algorithmic Discrimination Protections: You should not face discrimination by algorithms and systems should be used and designed in an equitable way. ● Data Privacy: You should be protected from abusive data practices via built-in protections and you should have agency over how data about you is used. ● Notice and Explanation: You should know that an automated system is being used and understand how and why it contributes to outcomes that impact you. 	<p>https://www.whitehouse.gov/ostp/ai-bill-of-rights/</p> <p>https://www.whitehouse.gov/wp-content/uploads/2022/10/Blueprint-for-an-AI-Bill-of-Rights.pdf</p>
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						<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Human Alternatives, Consideration, and Fallback: You should be able to opt out, where appropriate, and have access to a person who can quickly consider and remedy problems you encounter.	
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<p>National AI Strategy</p>	<p>35</p>	<p>Department for Science, Innovation & Technology, Office for Artificial Intelligence, Department for Digital, Culture, Media & Sport, Department for Business, Energy & Industrial Strategy</p>	<p>UK</p>	<p>Policy</p>	<p>Published 22 September 2021 Last updated 18 December 2022</p>	<p>The Strategy outlines the unique opportunities and challenges which AI presents and also, how AI can be used for the public benefit. It also outlines the expectations in the governance of AI in 10 years.</p>	<p>https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-ai-strategy</p>
<p>An assessment framework for non-discriminatory AI</p>	<p>36</p>	<p>Demos Helsinki, the University of Turku and the University of Tampere partnered up</p>	<p>Finnish</p>	<p>Policy</p>	<p>2022</p>	<p>The document consists of an assessment framework which assists developers to establish an equitable journey for the development of AI services <u>in the public sector</u>, from design to deployment.</p>	<p>https://demoshelsinki.fi/julkaisut/an-assessment-framework-for-non-discriminatory-ai/</p>

		to help the Finnish Government					
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<p>Impact Assessment: Fundamental rights and algorithm</p>	<p>37</p>	<p>Dutch Ministry of the Interior and Kingdom Relations</p>	<p>Netherlands</p>	<p>Legal</p>	<p>March 2022</p>	<p>This fundamental rights and algorithm impact assessment ('FRAIA') is a discussion and decision-making tool for government organizations. The tool facilitates an interdisciplinary dialogue by those responsible for the development and/or use of an algorithmic system. The commissioning client is primarily responsible for the (delegated) implementation of the FRAIA.</p> <p>The FRAIA comprises a large number of questions about the topics that need to be discussed and to which an answer must be formulated in any instance where a government organization considers developing, delegating the development of, buying, adjusting and/or using an algorithm (hereinafter for the sake of brevity: the use of or using an algorithm). Even when an algorithm is already being used, the FRAIA may serve as a tool for reflection. The discussion about the various questions should take place in a multidisciplinary team consisting of people with a wide range of specializations and backgrounds.</p>	<p>https://www.government.nl/binaries/government/documents/reports/2022/03/31/impact-assessment-fundamental-rights-and-algorithms/Fundamental+Rights+and+Algorithms+Impact+Assessment.pdf</p>
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						<p>Per question, the FRAIA indicates who should be involved in the discussion. This tool pays attention to all roles within a multidisciplinary team, which are included in the diagram below. However, the list is not exhaustive. Likewise, the role or function names may differ from one organization to another</p>	
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<p>Artificial Intelligence Act</p>	<p>38</p>	<p>Council of the European Union</p>	<p>European Union</p>	<p>Legal</p>	<p>11 November 2022</p>	<p>The Regulation pursues a number of overriding reasons of public interest, such as a high level of protection of health, safety and fundamental rights, and it ensures the free movement of AI-based goods and services cross-border, thus preventing Member States from imposing restrictions on the development, marketing and use of AI systems, unless explicitly authorized by this Regulation. AI systems identified as high-risk would include AI technology used in: safety components of regulated products; critical infrastructures; educational and vocational training; employment, workers management and access to self-employment; essential private and public services; law enforcement that may interfere with people’s fundamental rights; migration, asylum and border control management; and administration of justice and democratic processes. High-risk AI systems are to comply with specific requirements, which include the setting up of a sound risk management system, the use of high-quality datasets, appropriate</p>	<p>https://artificialintelligenceact.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/AIA-CZ-Draft-General-Approach-11-Nov-22.pdf</p>
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						<p>documentation to enhance traceability, the sharing of adequate information with the user, the design and implementation of appropriate human oversight measures, and the achievement of the highest standards of robustness, safety, cybersecurity and accuracy.</p>	
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<p>TTC Joint Roadmap for Trustworthy AI and Risk Management</p>	<p>39</p>	<p>European Commission</p>	<p>European</p>	<p>Policy and legislation</p>	<p>1 December 2022</p>	<p>This Joint Roadmap aims to guide the development of tools, methodologies, and approaches to AI risk management and trustworthy AI by the EU and the United States and to advance our shared interest in supporting international standardization efforts and promoting trustworthy AI on the basis of a shared dedication to democratic values and human rights.</p>	<p>https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/ttc-joint-roadmap-trustworthy-ai-and-risk-management</p>
<p>Roadmap for standing up a national AI resource</p>	<p>40</p>	<p>National Artificial Intelligence Research Resource Task Force</p>	<p>US</p>	<p>Implementation Plan</p>	<p>January 2023</p>	<p>This final report of the NAIRR Task Force presents a roadmap and implementation plan for a national cyberinfrastructure aimed at overcoming the access divide, reaping the benefits of greater brainpower and more diverse perspectives and experiences applied to developing the future of AI technology and its role in our society.</p>	<p>https://www.ai.gov/wp-content/uploads/2023/01/NAIRR-TF-Final-Report-2023.pdf</p>

<p>PLOT4ai (Assessment tool)</p>	<p>41</p>	<p>Private sector</p>	<p>European</p>	<p>Threat Modelling</p>	<p>2023</p>	<p>What is PLOT4ai? It is a library containing (at this moment) a collection of 86 different threats and a threat modeling methodology.</p> <p>With PLOT4ai it is possible to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> · Perform threat modeling on AI/ML systems Start doing Privacy by Design the right way · Create Responsible AI 	<p>https://plot4.ai/</p>
<p>Revised zero draft (framework) Convention on Artificial Intelligence, human rights, democracy and the rule of law</p>	<p>42</p>	<p>Council of Europe</p>	<p>European</p>	<p>Policy</p>	<p>6 January 2023</p>	<p>The Convention establishes certain fundamental principles, rules and rights aimed at ensuring that design, development and application of artificial intelligence systems is fully consistent with respect for human rights, the functioning of democracy and the observance of rule of law.</p>	<p>https://rm.coe.int/c-ai-2023-01-revised-zero-draft-framework-convention-public/1680aa193f</p>

<p>Biden executive order concerning AI algorithmic equity</p>	<p>43</p>	<p>White House</p>	<p>US</p>	<p>Legal</p>	<p>16 February 2023</p>	<p>The executive order also has provisions on algorithmic equity. It states that when designing, developing, acquiring, and using artificial intelligence and automated systems in the federal government, agencies shall do so, consistent with applicable law, in a manner that advances equity.</p>	<p>https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/presidential-actions/2023/02/16/executive-order-on-further-advancing-racial-equity-and-support-for-underserved-communities-through-the-federal-government/</p>
<p>Guidance on AI and data protection</p>	<p>44</p>	<p>Information Commissioner's Office</p>	<p>UK</p>	<p>Legal</p>	<p>15 March 2023</p>	<p>The guidance has a chapter with new high-level content on the transparency principle as it applies to AI. It also issues guidance on how to ensure lawfulness, fairness, and transparency in AI systems.</p>	<p>https://ico.org.uk/for-organisations/guide-to-data-protection/key-dp-themes/guidance-on-ai-and-data-protection/</p>

<p>AI Risk Management FW</p>	<p>45</p>	<p>NIST</p>	<p>US</p>	<p>Ethics</p>	<p>Latest release is 30 March</p>	<p>This is a step by step framework for any organization to see risks and align with risk level. Very flexible, NIST trustworthy</p> <p>On 26 January 2023, NIST released the AI Risk Management Framework (AI RMF 1.0) along with a companion NIST AI RMF Playbook, AI RMF Explainer Video, an AI RMF Roadmap, AI RMF Crosswalk, and various Perspectives.</p> <p>NIST AI RMF employs the following definitions: Note: additional considerations are underway to further align with international AI standards (including ISO/IEC 22989, ISO/IEC 23894 etc.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Risk: In the context of the AI RMF, ‘risk’ refers to the composite measure of an event’s probability of occurring and the magnitude (or degree) of the consequences of the corresponding events. The impacts, or consequences, of AI systems can be positive, negative, or both and can result in opportunities or threats (Adapted from ISO 31000:2018). 	<p>https://www.nist.gov/itl/ai-risk-management-framework</p>
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						<ul style="list-style-type: none">● Risk management: Risk management refers to coordinated activities to direct and control an organization with regard to risk (Source: ISO 31000:2018).● Risk tolerance: Refers to the organization's or stakeholder's readiness to bear risks in order to achieve its objectives. Risk tolerance can be influenced by legal or regulatory requirements (Adapted from: ISO Guide 73).● Socio-technical characteristics of AI trustworthiness: A system is considered trustworthy if it is valid and reliable, safe, fair, secure and with managed bias.	
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<p>AI: System v Processing, Means v Purposes</p>	<p>46</p>	<p>Spanish Data Protection Authority (AEPD)</p>	<p>Spain</p>	<p>Article</p>	<p>10 April 2023</p>	<p>It gives an example of an AI system used for recruiting and ways in which the controller can implement the system.</p>	<p>https://www.aepd.es/en/prensa-y-comunicacion/blog/ai-system-vs-processing-means-vs-purposes</p>
<p>Notice of the Cyberspace Administration of China on Public Comments on the "Administrative Measures for Generative Artificial Intelligence Services (Draft for Comment)" ("Generative AI" draft guidelines)</p>	<p>47</p>	<p>Cyberspace Administration of China - State Internet Information Office</p>	<p>China</p>	<p>Legal</p>	<p>11 April 2023</p>	<p>The draft guidelines outline the measures to be applied in order to promote the healthy development and standardized application of generative AI as well as the possible consequences for non-compliance with the guidelines.</p>	<p>http://www.cac.gov.cn/2023-04/11/c_1682854275475410.htm</p>

<p>Personal data processing that embed Artificial Intelligence</p>	<p>48</p>	<p>Spanish Data Protection Authority (AEPD)</p>	<p>Spain</p>	<p>Reference map</p>	<p>Unknown date</p>	<p>The reference map provides a roadmap to ensure compliance with data protection regulation.</p>	<p>https://www.aepd.es/documento/tramamientos-inteligencia-artificial-en.pdf</p>
<p>Artificial intelligence: the CNIL action plan</p>	<p>49</p>	<p>French Data Protection Authority (CNIL)</p>	<p>France</p>	<p>Legal/enforcement</p>	<p>16 May 2023</p>	<p>The CNIL has been working for several years to anticipate and respond to the issues raised by AI. In 2023, it will extend its action on augmented cameras and wishes to broaden its work to generative AI, large language models and derived applications (notably chatbots). Its action plan is based on 4 components: 1. understand how AI systems work and their impact on people; 2. enable and regulate the development of privacy-respecting AI; 3. unite and support innovative players in the AI ecosystem in France and Europe; 4. audit and control AI systems and protect people. This work will also make it possible to prepare for the entry into application of the draft European AI regulation, currently under discussion.</p>	<p>https://www.cnil.fr/fr/intelligence-artificielle-le-plan-daction-de-la-cnil</p>

<p>FACT SHEET: Biden-Harris Administration Announces New Actions to Promote Responsible AI Innovation that Protects Americans' Rights and Safety</p>	<p>50</p>	<p>US White House</p>	<p>US</p>	<p>Fact sheet</p>	<p>May 2023</p>	<p>The fact sheet recognizes that AI is one of the most powerful technologies of our time, but in order to seize the opportunities it presents, we must first mitigate its risks.</p>	<p>https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/statements-releases/2023/05/04/fact-sheet-biden-harris-administration-announces-new-actions-to-promote-responsible-ai-innovation-that-protects-americans-rights-and-safety/</p>
<p>FACT SHEET: Biden-Harris Administration Secures Voluntary Commitments from Leading Artificial Companies to Manage the Risks Posed by AI</p>	<p>51</p>	<p>US White House</p>	<p>US</p>	<p>Fact sheet</p>	<p>21 July 2023</p>	<p>The fact sheet recognizes a broader commitment by the Biden-Harris Administration to ensure AI is developed safely and responsibly, and to protect Americans from harm and discrimination</p>	<p>https://www.whitehouse.gov/briefing-room/statements-releases/2023/07/21/fact-sheet-biden-harris-administration-secures-voluntary-commitments-from-leading-artificial-intelligence-companies-to-</p>

							manage-the-risks-posed-by-ai/
Public comments on practical sheets on the creation of training databases for artificial intelligence (AI) systems		French Data Protection Authority (CNIL)	France	Practical sheets	12 October 2023	The French Data Protection Authority (CNIL) has responded to key players in the sector of creation of artificial intelligence (AI) systems and affirms that the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) supports an innovative and responsible approach towards the creation of AI systems. The CNIL is calling for innovative players that respect people and notes that the development of AI brings about great technological opportunities in all economic areas and society. For example, there are great opportunities in health, public services and business productivity.	

<p>1 First Algorithmic Risks Report Netherlands calls for additional action to control algorithmic and AI risks</p>	<p>52</p>	<p>Dutch Supervisory Authority (AP)</p>	<p>Netherlands</p>	<p>Report</p>	<p>1 September 2023</p>	<p>Innovations such as intelligent chatbots and the inadequate understanding by organizations of existing algorithms currently represent the most significant algorithmic risks in The Netherlands. This is highlighted in the inaugural Algorithm Risk Report Netherlands, published by the new Directorate of Algorithm Coordination at the Dutch Data Protection Authority (AP).</p>	<p>https://www.autoriteitpersoonsgegevens.nl/en/current/first-algorithmic-risks-report-netherlands-calls-for-additional-action-to-control-algorithmic-and-ai-risks</p>
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<p>Data protection office of the Principality of Liechtenstein issues guidance on data protection in chatbots</p>	<p>53</p>	<p>Data protection office of the Principality of Liechtenstein</p>	<p>Germany</p>	<p>Guidelines</p>	<p>27 October 2023</p>	<p>On October 27, 2023, the Supervisory Authority of Liechtenstein (DSS) published guidelines on using chatbots in compliance with data protection requirements. In particular, the DSS stated that operators must have a legal basis before processing personal data using chatbots, such as consent from the user, or contract fulfillment, if, for example, goods or services are ordered via a chatbot. However, the DSS explained that even with a legal basis, the principle of purpose limitation applies, and data processing must be limited to the purpose that users can reasonably expect when using a chatbot.</p>	<p>https://www.datenschutzstelle.li/datenschutz/themen-z/chatbots</p>
<p>President Biden Issues Executive Order on Safe, Secure, and Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence</p>	<p>54</p>	<p>US White House</p>	<p>US</p>	<p>Fact Sheet</p>	<p>30 October 2023</p>	<p>The Executive Order establishes new standards for AI safety and security, protects Americans’ privacy, advances equity and civil rights, stands up for consumers and workers, promotes innovation and competition, advances American leadership around the world, and more.</p>	<p>FACT SHEET: President Biden Issues Executive Order on Safe, Secure, and Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence The White House</p>

<p>Legal basis for data protection when using AI</p>	<p>55</p>	<p>The Baden-Württemberg Commissioner for Data Protection and Freedom of Information</p>	<p>Germany</p>	<p>Paper</p>	<p>7 November 2023</p>	<p>The paper is intended to help responsible bodies in Baden-Württemberg to deal with the legal basis that data protection law provides for the use of systems of so-called artificial intelligence (hereinafter: AI). The starting point is the applicable law. The requirements of the regulation establishing harmonized regulations for artificial intelligence of the European Union (hereinafter: AI regulation) which have not yet been finally negotiated, are at best touched upon. The designation as a discussion paper is intended to underline that these are not final determinations - even with regard to individual points - but that the paper is intended to reflect the status of the discussion.</p>	<p>https://www.baden-wuerttemberg.datenschutz.de/rechtsgrundlagen-datenschutz-ki/</p>
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<p>OECD adopted its revised definition of Artificial Intelligence</p>	<p>56</p>	<p>The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development's (OECD) Council</p>	<p>US</p>	<p>Principles</p>	<p>8 November 2023</p>	<p>The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development's (OECD) Council on 8 November adopted the new definition of Artificial Intelligence that is set to be incorporated in the EU's new AI rulebook. "An AI system is a machine-based system that, for explicit or implicit objectives, infers, from the input it receives, how to generate outputs such as predictions, content, recommendations, or decisions that [can] influence physical or virtual environments. Different AI systems vary in their levels of autonomy and adaptiveness after deployment," reads the new definition.</p>	<p>https://www.oecd.org/digital/artificial-intelligence/</p>
<p>Checklist for using LLM-based chatbots</p>	<p>57</p>	<p>Hamburg Data Protection Authority</p>	<p>Germany</p>	<p>Checklist</p>	<p>13 November 2023</p>	<p>The DPA in Hamburg published a checklist intended to serve as a guide for companies and authorities on the data protection-compliant use of LLM-based chatbots. As a general rule, if the provider of a chatbot has allowed the chatbot to use data for its own purposes in the terms and conditions, no personal data may be transmitted to the AI.</p>	<p>https://datenschutz-hamburg.de/news/heckliste-zum-einsatz-llm-basierter-chatbots</p>

Guidelines for Secure AI System Development	58	The UK National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC) and the US Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA)	UK & US	Guidelines	27 November 2023	<p>The UK National Cyber Security Centre (NCSC) and the US Cybersecurity and Infrastructure Security Agency (CISA) (in cooperation with industry experts and 21 other international agencies and ministries) launched the 'Guidelines for Secure AI System Development' that will help developers of any systems that use AI make informed cyber security decisions at every stage of the development process.</p> <p>The guidelines focus on 4 key areas: (1) secure design, (2) secure development, (3) secure deployment, and (4) secure operation and maintenance.</p>	<p>NCSC develops new global guidelines for AI security - NCSC.GOV.UK</p>